

Cruise Report

**NOAA Ship *Ron Brown* / ROV *Jason* Expedition RB-1903
April 9 to April 30, 2019**

for

DEEP SEARCH

**DEEP Sea Exploration to Advance Research
on Coral/Canyon/Cold seep Habitats**

**Deepwater Atlantic Habitats II:
Continued Atlantic Research and Exploration
in Deepwater Ecosystems with Focus on
Coral, Canyon and Seep Communities
Contract - M17PC00009**

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Expedition Background

The RB1903 expedition on board the NOAA Ship *Ron Brown* with the ROV *Jason* is the fifth cruise of the project, and the second submersible sampling cruise. The primary goals of this cruise are as follows:

1. Exploration of new sites and new areas within known sites
2. Sampling of corals and associated fauna for biodiversity and biogeography
3. Community sampling at seep and coral habitats
4. Sediment sampling at soft sediment sites for biogeochemistry and diversity
5. Collections of corals for live coral experiments
6. Water sampling for water chemistry and microbial diversity
7. Sediment, water, and faunal samples for eDNA work
8. Geological observations and sampling for geomorphology
9. Lander deployments

Cruise Summary Table

Date	Location	Latitude	Longitude	depth	Jason dive	CTD cast	Activities
5-Apr	Charleston, SC						ROV mobe
6-Apr	Charleston, SC						ROV mobe
7-Apr	Charleston, SC						ROV mobe
8-Apr	Charleston, SC						ROV mobe
9-Apr	depart Charleston, transit to Stetson Shallow					CTD01	depart 1400, arrive 2200, CTD cast, attempt to hold station but 3 knots current
10-Apr	Richardson Hills	32	-77.43	790	J2-1128	CTD02	arrive 0630, deploy USBL pole, 0700 CTD cast, 0900 deploy elevator for USBL calibration, 2000 ROV launch
11-Apr	Richardson Hills	31.88	-77.374	800		CTD03, 04	1000 recover ROV, 1030 deploy lander, 1100 triangulation, 1300 2x CTD, 1800 turn for port for crew family emergency
12-Apr	Richardson Hills						transit back to Richardson, move on to mapping ops from Richardson to Blake Deep
13-Apr	Richardson Hills	31.985	-77.413		J2-1129	CTD05, 06, 07	0800 recover lander, 1000 CTD cast @ Richardson A4963, 1200 launch Jason
14-Apr	Richardson Hills						0900 recover Jason, 1100 deploy lander, triangulate, transit to Popenoe Mounds, MBES over Hoyt Hills on the way
15-Apr	Blake Mounds	31.079	-79.492	600			arrive 1000, weather conditions forced an early return to port
16-Apr	Charleston - Savanna Banks				J2-1130	CTD08	Arrive Charleston by 08:00, depart Charleston 1200, head to Savannah Banks, CTD on arrival, Dive: 1800
17-Apr	Blake Deep	31.079	-79.492	600	J2-1131		recover: 0800, head to Blake Deep, CTD, dive 2000

Date	Location	Latitude	Longitude	depth	Jason dive	CTD cast	Activities
18-Apr	Blake Deep	31.293	-77.243	1300		CTD09	recover 0800, CTD, level-wind test, transit to Moorehead City
19-Apr	Morehead City						weather issues
20-Apr	Cape Lookout	34.32424	-75.78643	500			18:00-22:00 transit map Lookout deep, transit to Pamlico Canyon
21-Apr	Pamlico Canyon	34.956	-75.224	600	J2-1132	CTD10	triangulate the lander upon arrival (3 hrs), CTD:0800, Dive: 12:00
22-Apr	Pamlico, Pea Island	35.675	-74.797	200		CTD11	recover: 16:00, CTD: 17:00, transit to Pea Island seep ~0000, dive: 0000
23-Apr	Pea Island, Kitty Hawk Seep	35.932	-74.816	285	J2-1133	CTD12, 13	dive: 0:00-12:00, recover: 12 or 16:00, CTD x2 (4hrs), transit to Kitty Hawk (2hrs)
24-Apr	Kitty Hawk, Keller Canyon	35.531	-74.852	300	J2-1134	CTD14	dive: 0:00-12:00, CTD: 13:00, transit to Keller (2hrs), no dive (currents)
25-Apr	Lookout Deep	33.923	-75.812	1200	J2-1135	CTD15	dive 1400-1700, CTD, weather building
26-Apr	Blake Ridge Seep	32.494	-76.199	2200			mapping ops, weather
27-Apr	Blake Ridge Seep	32.494	-76.199	2200	J2-1136	CTD16	dive: 0000-1600, recover, transit to Blake Seep (4 hrs) , CTD, dive: 0000
28-Apr	Cape Fear Seep	32.975	-75.933	2600	J2-1137	CTD17	dive: 0000-2359
29-Apr	Richardson West	31.894	-77.698	700	J2-1138	CTD18	recover: 0400, CTD: 0730-1000, dive start transit to Charleston
30-Apr	return to Charleston						arrive 1200
1-May	Charleston, SC						DEMOB
2-May	Charleston, SC						DEMOB

General Dive Plans

Each dive will have a specific plan based on the type of habitat, the sampling needs at the site, the capacity of the *Jason* “basket,” the results of the previous dive(s), and the overall needs of the entire project. Although much of this information will only be available the evening before the dive, there is enough existing information to present generalized dive plans for the three habitats that are the focus of this study: canyons, corals, and cold seeps.

Canyons: The canyon dives will focus on coral diversity, biogeochemistry, macro-infauna, geology, and water sampling. If bubble plumes and seeps are present, they will also be investigated. Dives will begin in the deepest parts of the chosen targets, and proceed upslope.

Basket: 11 push cores on port swing arm, 14 push cores on the basket, 8 sample quivers on swing arm, 6 on the basket, 4 niskins, 5-chamber slurp, 1 large biobox, 3 mussel pots (if seeps present), additional sample quivers (if seeps are not present)

Priorities: corals for barcoding, key coral and mussel species with associates for pop gen, push cores in canyon axis and near corals and/or mussels (if possible), water samples near scleractinians and large coral colonies, rocks for geology

Corals: These dive plans are primarily focused on the *Lophelia*-dominated habitats in the southern part of the study area.

Basket: 11 push cores on swing arms, 8 sample quivers on swing arms, 4 niskins, 5-chamber slurp, 2 large bioboxes, 3 coral pots, rock boxes, additional sample quivers

Priorities: video survey of distinct geomorphologies identified from new and existing multibeam data, coral community samples, push cores associated with and away from community samples, water samples near the seafloor where live corals are present, rocks (if present), other corals for barcoding, *Lophelia* in bioboxes for live coral experiments

Seeps: The dive plans for the deep seep sites where mussels are present (i.e. Cape Fear) and shallow sites that are dominated by bacterial mats (i.e. Pea Island) will be similar with the replacement of the mussel pots with additional push cores at the shallow sites.

Basket: 25 push cores on swing arms, 14 sample quivers, 8 on swing arms, 6 on the basket, 4 niskins, 5-chamber slurp, 1 large biobox, 2 mussel pots (if seeps present), rock boxes, additional push cores and sample quivers (if seeps are not present)

Priorities: Mussel community sampling, push cores associated with community samples and away, mussel sampling into bioboxes for pop gen plus gill/host genomics, water samples associated with all mussel samples, coral samples (if present), carbonates

Expedition Activities

April 5

Jason mobilization begins with the arrival of the four Jason vans plus the rad van on the crane barge. All of these were loaded onto the ship and installation begins. Shipments from the science party including hand-carried packages and pallets are also brought on board using the ship's crane.

Nancy Prouty from USGS reports that she has strep throat, so she is replaced by Lauren Carroll from Mandy Joye's group.

April 6-7

Additional members of the science party arrive and mobilization continues. There are problems encountered with rigging the rad van. Eventually, it is determined that there is a ground in the power cable coming from the van. Issues with the port ship's crane overheating slow the process, with the lander still on the pier and an inability to move large items on the deck.

April 8

The remaining members of the science party arrive in the morning and everyone moves on board. An electrician is scheduled to address the problem with the rad van. A frayed wire is located on the connection from the van to the ship's power supply and this repair eliminates the ground. Issues with the port crane overheating continue and the lander remains on the pier.

The ship departs at noon for a test of the recently rebuilt generator in the harbor. While this is ongoing, a trip to the NOAA Hollings lab is completed to fill the liquid nitrogen dewars (there is no -80°C freezer on board).

The ship notifies us that the original crew member scheduled for the cruise is now healthy and can sail for the entire length of the cruise. That results in a shuffling of the berthing since that person (a male) is replacing a male on leg 1 and a female on leg 2.

April 9

We are scheduled to depart at 1000, but this is delayed while the crane repairs are finalized and the lander is then loaded onto the ship. The ship finally departs at approximately 1400 hrs.

2200 **CTD-01** in Stetson Shallow

We arrive at a location in the Stetson Shallow region with sufficient water depth (> 500 m) to conduct the USBL calibration with the elevator. The USBL pole is deployed and a CTD cast is conducted to generate a sound velocity profile and collect a series of water column samples.

April 10

When the CTD cast is complete at approximately 0130, the ship attempts to hold station, but is not able to in the ~3 knots of current that are present here. The Gulf Stream is significantly further west now than it was in August. We continue on to the Richardson Hills sites on the other side of the Gulf Stream.

0700 **CTD-02** Richardson Hills

We arrive and the surface currents are just under 1 knot. We lower the USBL pole and conduct a CTD cast, generating a water-column profile with the CTD and firing niskin bottles near the seafloor (21) and near the surface (3).

0900 Elevator deployment

The elevator is deployed in a flat spot along the eastern edge of the “U” that separates the Stetson Banks sites to the west from the Richardson Hills sites to the east. Then the ship molds station at a series of cardinal points and determines the range and bearing to the elevator to complete the USBL calibration.

1900 Elevator recovery

2000 Launch **J2-1128** at Richardson Hills swale site

On the descent, we crossed a clear thermocline at approximately 750m, far deeper than normal, but similar to the water column profile over the other Lophelia mounds at the northern reef track at Richardson Hills.

The ROV landed immediately on coral rubble habitat with abundant live Lophelia colonies. Ivan took the controls to get the camera dialed in. He determined that frequent white balancing of the camera will greatly improve the color temperature of the image, particularly when you go from sitting down to transiting or vice versa. We then began a series of octocoral collections - there were abundant Plumarella and neptheids throughout, and patches of a white plexaurid from time to time. The first swale was mostly this type of habitat with live Lophelia colonies in the “bush” stage with some Madrepora and a few Solenosmilia mixed in. The second swale near WPT 2 was mostly coral rubble with very little live coral consisting of smaller colonies of Lophelia and occasionally Enallopsamia.

The bottom of the swale between WPT 2 and 3 was finer sediments with clear bedforms of sand and small rubble. As we began to climb up towards WPT 3, there was mostly rubble with large numbers of small, white plexaurid colonies. At the top near WPT 3, we encountered another field of standing dead coral with numerous live coral colonies interspersed. We set up for the first coral pot sample here, and then made a live coral collection into the biobox. Leaving WPT 3, the coral cover began to decline on the way to WPT 4.

We continued along the track from WPT 4 to 5, and observed coral rubble in the swales/furrows between the peaks, with dense live *Lophelia* on the highs. The structure below the live *Lophelia* appeared to be a dense matrix of dead *Lophelia* and fine and sandy sediments. We collected MP2, soft coral, *Plumarella*, and *Lophelia* into a quiver and biobox during the watch. Fish observations included rattails (e.g., *Nezumia*), snaphobranchid eels, and a goosefish (*Lophiodes*). Depth ranged from ~747 to 773 m. There was a noticeable shimmer in the water around these topographic highs, consistent with water temperature changes.

Near WPT5, on the flank close to the top of a small feature at approximately 780 meters, the substrate was mostly coral rubble with white plexurid octocorals plus sponges. We collected one of the white plexurids as a representative of this habitat. As we continued up the feature, we came across occasional *Enallopsammia profunda* colonies, most were the yellow morph, but a few were white. We collected some of each. An invertebrate that was conspicuous was the pinkish *Echinus* urchin. We continued upslope towards WPT 6. At approximately 750 m, the temperature began to climb sharply, from 4.4 to 6.5 degrees C at 760 m, then to about 10 degrees at 730 m. We traversed across a swale with coral rubble/sandy substrate before climbing to WPT6, where there was again a higher abundance of large live coral colonies in the warmer waters. Here we began to see occasional *Madrepora oculata*. We collected *M. oculata* and *Lophelia*, plus *Plumarella*. Within about 5 minutes, we observed 3 chimeara with black spots.

The transit between 6 and 7 was mainly along the top of a ridge. At WPT 7, there were numerous large live *Lophelia* colonies. Some of these were approaching the thicket stage, with rings or semi-circles of live coral growing around a center consisting of standing dead skeleton. In some places, these structures were so large that they had tipped over and the live coral continued to grow at the edges.

April 11

ROV was off bottom at 0730, but the level-wind was not functioning and there was a wrap in the winch. The ship moved to the NE into deeper water and the ROV was lowered back to the bottom. Recovery was slow and methodical, but avoided any further mishaps.

1000 recover J2-1128

1030 launch **lander** @ Richardson Hills

1100 triangulate lander position

The lander was deployed at a site approximately 1 km NE of the area that was just surveyed on the previous dive. The intent is for the lander to stay down for ~48 hours collecting data then we will return to recover and redeploy it in a nearby location.

1330 **CTD-03** at Richardson Hills swale site

1500 **CTD-04** at Richardson Hills swale site

The first CTD (03) was to collect bottom water for the live coral tanks and buckets in the cold room. The second CTD (04) was for a complete water column profile roughly half way between the lander position and the end of the J2-1128 dive.

The winds and seas were consistently climbing all day, so we moved to mapping operations. A survey was planned to fill the gaps in the bathymetry between the Richardson Hills and Blake Deep sites. However, at this time, one of the crew members had a family emergency, and the ship turned to transit to the nearest port, which is Cape Fear near Wilmington NC.

April 12

We arrived inside the fairway at Cape Fear at 0700 and a Costa Guard boat came out to meet us and transfer the crew member. We then turned and headed back out towards the Richardson sites. The weather continued to be too rough for an ROV deployment, so we ran two mapping lines between Richardson Hills and Blake Deep.

April 13

At 0630, we broke off of the multibeam line and transited over to the lander site. Just after 0800, we triggered the release of the lander. It was successfully recovered around 0900. It seemed to be a successful deployment with plenty of data from all of the instruments, and a large number of amphipods inside of the fish that were deployed with the baited camera.

We then transited to the Richardson Hills site where Alvin dive 4963 took place. We took 3 CTD casts, the first for bottom water and the second and third for a full water column profile. The 2nd cast was to the northeast, downstream from the site, and the 3rd cast was to the southwest, upstream of the site (the current was approximately 1.5 knots at a heading of 060). We then waited until the sea state declined to launch the ROV at this site.

1130 **CTD-05** at Richardson Hills A4963 site

1300 **CTD-06** at Richardson Hills A4963 site

1600 **CTD-07** at Richardson Hills A4963 site

1900 Launch **J2-1129** at Richardson Hills A4963

We launched the vehicle about 1.5 nautical miles SW (upstream) of the seafloor target. The Jason group wanted to text their level-wind on the way down so we decided to allow for the drift of the ship in the 1+ knot surface currents. On the descent, the temperature dropped steadily the entire time. At 450 m, it was approximately 16 deg C, and at 650 m it was 11 deg C. On the seafloor at 725 m, it was around 9 deg C.

Occasionally during the dive, the shimmering water of the thermocline was observed at depth.

At 2014 local time, the bottom was in sight. We set up on bottom and immediately looked for a place to deploy the McLean pump. We came across the large 3m high marker that was deployed with the coral transplant experiment, but it was in a different location, just down hill from the deployment site. This was a relatively flat area of rubble surrounded by live coral cover on the side of the coral mound, so we set the McLean pump here at 2046 local and used the marker to relocate the pump at the end of the dive.

As we came off the bottom, we turned towards the transplant target and almost immediately found them. The three cement blocks with the stained coral were retrieved into the starboard biobox without incident. However, we had a very hard time closing the box even though it was not apparently fouled in any way. Between 2130 and 2200 hrs, we shot a series of highlight video in this area of large live *Lophelia* colonies on a fairly steep slope.

We set down at a new location and collected a series of *Plumarella*, *Anthothela*, and a few sponges into the quivers. We moved over a bit to a relatively undisturbed location and collected a coral pot sample and a few more collections into the quivers. We then moved again to take another coral pot in a nearby location, and some live *Lophelia* into the port biobox.

April 14

The ROV picked up and traversed to WPT 2 on the north side of the mound, away from the Alvin dive tracks in the area. We collected *Madrepora*, *Plumarella*, unknown white plexaurid, and a cup coral. We also collected an unknown yellow plexaurid and *Anthomastus*. The area was composed of lots of standing dead *Lophelia* capped with dense branches of live *Lophelia*. A few globular sponges that looked like large golf balls were also observed. There were a few fish observed while transiting up the slope, including *Nezumia*, *Laemonema?*, and synphobranchids. At 0223 we started to head toward the McLane pump to start the multibeam patch test at a known target. The seafloor was visible during the multibeam ops, with dense particulate organic matter visible in the water column. There was a time code issue with the 4K camera, where some of the video was collected with an incorrect time code. The issue was corrected. During the MB patch test, the plan was to run lines at different elevations at particular headings to calibrate pitch and roll. Overall resolution of the MB will be ~ 0.5m. At 0345, the survey began, with 5.5 survey lines completed by 0929. During trackline 6, the current was too fast (0.5 kt to the NE) for the ROV to remain on heading and make way, so the decision to break the line was made. It was not possible to complete the cross line, so the plan changed to head to the seafloor and collect samples.

At 0600 local time, we returned to the seafloor on the SW flank of the mound. We deployed marker 1 at 31d59.051 N, 77d24.675 W and then collected Madrepora, Lophelia, and 3 Plumarella colonies into the biobox. We took some nice highlight video in this area after the collections.

At 0645, the wind had come up to about 20 knots, with gusts to 25, and the weather was predicted to get worse throughout the day, so the dive was given 30 minutes until leaving bottom. We took the last mussel pot sample and deployed marker 2 at this location. We then transited over to the pump deployment site, over some very large, tipped-over, live Lophelia colonies, and set up to retrieve the pump. By 0715, the pump was on board and secure. We attempted to fire all of the niskins, but only the two smaller niskins actually triggered. At 0730, we left bottom.

0900 Recover **J2-1129** from Richardson A4963 site

Recovery took a long time because of the persistent issues with the Jason winch level-wind system. At a number of points, the vehicle had to be lowered again to take wraps out of the winch. After recovery, the weight for the lander was repositioned, and the ship began to transit over to the lander deployment location.

1100 Deploy **Albex lander** at Richardson Hills site.

The lander was deployed from the same surface position as before. It was then triangulated in to get a good fix on it at its resting place on the seafloor. It will remain there until the next cruise, which is not scheduled yet, but should occur some time in September – October 2019. Once we were done with the triangulation, then we transited to the Blake Mounds site over night.

April 15

We arrived at the Blake Mounds site in the morning after a very rough transit. Once we were set up in position at the site, we tested the ability of the ship to hold station. The currents were up to 3 knots, which made it very difficult for any operations. We then went north to the Savannah Banks sites, where the current was approximately 1.5 knots. However, the seas remained at 5-7 feet and the winds were a sustained 20-25 knots. Therefore, the decision was made to head into port early in the hope that we could get the transfer completed in the morning and get back out to sea early on the 16th when the weather was supposed to be better.

April 16

We transferred 11 new science personnel on board. Headed to Savannah Banks to conduct **CTD08** followed by a long dive, **J2-1130**. The winch level wind was not functioning well so the ROV team did a test to see what adjustments need to be made to the end stop for each wrap. During descent, there was a significant amount of POM in the water column and squid. On the way to WP1, we saw some octocorals

(*Pseudodrifia*) and cup corals and some live and dead *Lophelia* and collected a coral pot. The sediment had too much coral rubble to enable push coring. Other corals observed during the transit upslope included

Throughout the transit from WPT 1 to WPT 2 there was an increase in coral rubble and live coral density as the ROV moved upslope. During the first portion of the transit there was a lot of coral (likely *Lophelia pertusa*) rubble without much live coral except small colonies of stylasterid and nephtheid corals. Then the rubble became denser and the occurrence of live *Lophelia pertusa* thickets increased. As the ROV continued upslope the currents increased to around 1 knot and there were sightings of *Madrepora* and *Enallopsammia* (both yellow and white morphs). Around 0630 (depth?) there was a shift in dominant scleractinian coral from *Lophelia pertusa* to *Enallopsammia* (white morph). Amongst the coral rubble primnoids (*Plumarella*), cup corals (*Thecapsammia*), Nephtheids (*Pseudodrifia*), and sponges were common. There was also a number (>5) of small shark seen throughout the area. At WPT 2 (511m) there was live *Enallopsammia* and the diversity of corals listed above. Downslope from WPT2 the coral diversity suddenly halted and there was almost no live scleractinians and much less rubble. There was very high current with a lot of particulate in the water. Throughout this time, we collected two mussel pots of *Lophelia*, one large live *Lophelia* collection, *Madrepora*, *Plumarella*, *Pseudodrifia*, cup corals, *Enallopsammia* (white and yellow), and sponges. One notable observation was of a shark eating a squid while conducting a live *lophelia* collection. Also noticed that the large urchins are primarily in the rubble areas and not with the live coral. Overall, there were several collections of target corals (e.g., *Enallopsammia*, *Madrepora*, *Lophelia*, etc.). Ultimately, we were able to collect push core in the coral rubble next to the *Pseudodrifia* and near *Enallopsammia*. Collected another mussel pot on a small patch of live *lophelia* with dead coral matrix. Fish observed included catshark, chimaeria, *Nezumia*, scorpaenids. We tripped all 4 niskins at the end of the dive near *Enallopsammia*, but the aft niskin didn't close all of the way because it had shifted during the dive. We left bottom at 1138 UTC and saw lots of POM during ascent.

April 17

Recover ROV, transited to Blake Deep, then another dive, **J2-1131**. Reached bottom at 0106 UTC. Observed several coral species including bamboos and anthipatharians. We attempted to push core but were unable to collect at the beginning of the dive due to the substrate. Between WTP 1 and WPT 2 there was sedimented bottom with octocorals and black corals growing on occasional rock outcrops. The slope up to WPT 2 was not very steep and was very sedimented. The transit between WPT 2 and WPT 3 yielded highly sedimented rocks and interesting geology with sediment/rock shelves all the way up the ridge. At the top of the ridge (1314 m) was a rock overhang (~.5-1 meter thick) with *Desmophyllum*, *anthomastus*, black corals, anemones, and bamboo corals. At

1311 meters there was a sedimented area below the ridge and four push cores were collected. The ROV came around the “nose” of the ridge at WPT 3 and the community did not change much but there were bigger boulders, however everything was still very sedimented. Starting between WPT 3 and 4 there were sparse corals on small sedimented rocks on a not very steep slope. Headed downslope to WPT 4 to try and do some push cores but there were too many rocks so headed back up slope. Throughout this time, we collected *Solenosammilia*, *Hemicorallium*, *Iridogorgia*, black coral, yellow plexaurids + *Astroschema*, dead bamboo coral skeleton, *Metallogorgia*, *Desmophyllum*, *Chrysogorgia*, *Lethothela*, *Swiftia*, and 4 push cores. Continuing on to WP4, the corals encountered were similar to those found at the first part of the dive, including yellow plexaurids, *Solenosmilia*, and unknown bamboo. We collected some nice imagery of a rock with large vase sponges, bamboo, *Solenosmilia*, *Chrysogorgia*, and *desmophyllum*. Also observed a few different types of seapens. Four more push cores were collected. Rock samples were collected as well. At 1149 UTC, we reached the top of the feature where we tripped the niskins and observed a fish with several parasites. A few more plexaurids and a *Chrysogorgia* were collected before coming off bottom at 1433 UTC.

April 18

Recover ROV, **CTD-09**, then transited to 2000 m water depth location for level wind test because of issues with ROV winch. The winch was not wrapping consistently and changing direction prematurely. Test was successful. Transited to Morehead City.

April 19

Transit to Morehead City to wait out the weather.

April 20

Departed Morehead City and transited to mapping site at Cape Lookout, where we collected high resolution multibeam bathymetry for ~4 hours over target area identified from the predictive models. We then started transiting to Pamlico Canyon ~ 2230 local.

April 21

Around 0400 am local, we set up to triangulate the lander. This procedure went well and we were able to locate and triangulate a position of the Pamlico lander. The surface current was ~3kt to the NE. **CTD-10** with moncore started around 0800 local, at a location northwest of our dive target in a gully area at 1300 m. The current was strong and made the CTD cast very challenging. While we were able to collect a bottom sediment sample with the moncore, it likely hit the side of the canyon due to the significant wire angle that occurred throughout the cast. This was due to the fact that the USBL pole made it impossible for the ship to back down in order to straighten the wire.

The ROV launch was ~1200 for ROV dive **J2-1132** at Pamlico Canyon on Easter Sunday and there was chocolate and candy for all. This dive started at the base of the canyon at around ~1800 m and continued upslope. The bottom was heavily sedimented with a steep slope and there were *Acesta* shells observed. Sediment cores were collected at several locations throughout the dives, on sedimented ledges. At 2049 UTC, we collected some rock samples and *Acanthogorgia* ~ 1700 m. Transiting from WP1 to WP2, there were a series of rock steps and ledges, mainly populated by sea stars and ophiuroids. Near WP2, at the base of a wall, the second set of push cores (7 total) were collected. While transiting from WP2 to WP3, we began to see lots of brisingid sea stars and small underhang communities of *Solenosmilia*, *Desmophyllum*, and some colonies of *Acanthogorgia*. Two slurp collections were made of *Solenosmilia* and *Desmophyllum* from these communities (blue and black containers). Upon reaching WP3, we took a set of 6 push cores. All equipment on the ROV worked fine, but the vessel was having difficulty holding station on occasion with the wind and current. One occasion we left bottom for a few minutes while the ship stabilized, but otherwise managed to maintain normal operations. The overall dive plan was to work laterally along the northern steep canyon wall in a northwest direction. Dense coral communities were observed under the terrace overhangs. These communities were dominated by *Solenosmilia variabilis*, *Desmophyllum dianthus* and *Acanthogorgia* sp. The fileshell *Acesta* sp was also commonly observed amongst the corals. We moved upslope to explore a different depth range (~1350-1300m) but despite abundant exposed hard substrate at these depths, the habitat was almost devoid of megafauna. The bathymetry contours were tending to spread further apart as we moved WNW up-canyon, so we decided to move back down-slope to the steeper walls. Throughout the dive, several collections were made of dominant corals, *Acesta* and other fauna using slurp, quivers and bioboxes. Representative rock samples were also collected. Due to the length of the dive, we were able to make our way through most of the planned waypoints, covering space over a large vertical and lateral gradient, as well as distinct changes in the seafloor geological morphology.

April 22

Continued dive, delayed recovery until after 1600 local because a storm blew through and the seastate picked up. Notable observations also include trash (e.g., monofilament) throughout the dive. The ROV was off bottom at 1853 UTC, ~1185m.

Planned CTD ops directly after USBL recovery took a few hours because set up and drift required setting up the ship ~3 miles southwest of the 1600m depth target in Pamlico Canyon. While deploying **CTD-11**, it became clear that with the USBL pole in the water, it was not possible for the ship to back down to enable a straight wire angle.

The CTD reached the seafloor at ~1130m within the canyon. Camera on CTD confirmed that we reached the seafloor with a clear image of a crab.

April 23

Dive at Pea Island seep, **J2-1133**. The overall plan was to investigate seep targets in the southern cluster (Pea Island C) where we have good Sentry imagery of seep carbonate, mats, and dense fishes. At 0626 UTC, the ROV was headed to the seafloor, with lots of POM and midwater fishes observed on descent. Several seep targets were placed on the underlay to help guide the dive. At 0634 UTC, the ROV reached bottom (354.8 m), and we encountered lots of fish, including black bellied rosefish, and low visibility overall. At 0707, bubbles were observed as well as lots of pits and mounds on the sediment surface. At 0750, cores were collected within mat sediments and bubbles released during the coring (330 m). When collecting a rock sample (0914 UTC), a tubeworm appeared after a piece of rock was broken off of a larger carbonate sample. The tubeworm and rock sample were collected. This was the first tubeworm that we have observed in the US Atlantic seeps to date. Lots of squid were present, along with long-finned hake?, and anemones. A few more rock samples were collected throughout the dive. All equipment on the vehicle worked fine, there was a moderate current coming from the north that occasionally re-suspended sediment and reduced visibility. Surface current and winds were minimal and the ship held station well. Around WP6, patchy, moderate sized bacterial mats were observed on the flat sedimented periphery, and large discrete authigenic carbonate mounds were common in the center of the feature. These were densely colonized by *Actinoschypia*, zoanthids and anemones. On one occasion a colony of *Lophelia* (11.5 deg C, ~ 280 m) was observed and a sample collected. Several *Eumunida picta* were associated with the coral colony. No seep-endemic megafauna were observed, but this appeared to be a highly productive site, as evidenced by the large number of fishes (Jacks, Blackbelly Rosefish, *Lymonema*, Cusk-type fish and eels) and crabs. Collections of 16 push cores (in active seep site with bubbles and off-seep), and 4 water samples (1 in bubbles and 3 next to bacterial mats) were made in addition to the coral sample. The cores were covered with an tarp to avoid loss due to degassing during ascent. The ROV was off bottom at 1601 (300m).

CTD casts 12 and 13 were conducted at Pea Island, off seep and on seep, respectively. Following the casts, we transited north to Kitty Hawk seep.

Dive at Kitty Hawk, **J2-1134**: Launch planned at 2000 with a long dive planned (~16hrs). At ~0050 the ROV was 30 m off bottom, with lots of swimmers, dense POM, and mid water fishes observed. At 0054, the ROV lost power, which was returned at 0057 UTC. At 0102, bottom was in site, with lots of quill worms and a scorpaenid on the seafloor (466.8m). Other fish observed included a snipe eel, paralepidid (cf. barracudina), eel pouts, and black bellied rosefish. Other animals included lithodid or spider crabs,

flounders, and many squat lobsters. We slurped several of these *E. picta*, but the slurp chamber wasn't indexed correctly, so they remained mostly in the slurp hose until later in the dive when the chamber was adjusted. Continuing on to WP2, we encountered bubbles and white mat, and a rocky area with a vestimentiferan tube worm (0215 UTC). Following imaging the tube worm and during the collection of the worm's rock, a ground fault occurred (0226 UTC) with the rock in the manipulator. When power was restored (0232UTC) , the rock had been dropped, but it didn't take long to find it and collect the worm and the rock (0245). We also saw some sort of ray. As we transitioned over soft sediment (400m), we continued to see spider crabs and swimming shrimp with long antennae.

April 24

At 0442 (UTC), another ground fault occurred, which was resolved by 0447. Upon heading back along the track and while continuing to chase sonar targets, it was noted that another tubeworm was observed on a large carbonate formation. Throughout the dive, we observed a few tubeworms on rocky substrate. We also found some areas with active bubbling ~360 and collected some good imagery and push cores. Additional cores were collected within mat environments (0849 UTC) at 334 m. As we transited to shallower depths, we also saw some large megafauna, including sharks [e.g., hammerhead], conger?, large manta ray, sea robin, flounder and lobsters. While we were on the lookout for live clams, none were found, but we did see trash and collected a plastic spoon (~220m). Toward the end of the dive, there appeared a series of linear ridge features on the sonar, apparently low profile bed forms. Jason was off bottom at 1550 UTC (213m).

Following recovery, we conducted **CTD-14**, and then transited to Keller. On station at ~1600. Given the 3 back to back dives at Pamlico and the two seep sites, time was needed to turn the basket around and prepare for the next dive. Planned dive at 0000 on the 25th. Current and wind look good, conditions to dive were good throughout the evening until ~2030 when the current picked up to 4.9 kt. At 2200, the bridge, EL, and Chief Sci decided that the conditions were prohibitive for diving, so we set a course for the deep Cape Lookout site, allowing us to test the habitat suitability models developed for the area.

April 25

Dive at cape lookout deep, **J2-1135**. The plan was for a relatively short dive here before the weather started to pick up and push us south. At 1924, the ROV had landed slightly deeper than 1000 m on sediment, with scattered small bacterial mats. Push cores were collected within the mats, as well as suction samples. There were few invertebrate megafauna, but moderately abundant fishes of various types (*Nezumia*, *Coryphaenoides*, *Synaphobranchid* eels). We transited to the NW towards a steeper structure that had been interpreted as a wall. During the transit we came across a pile of

boulders of a black material. They were sparsely colonized by sponges, octocorals (Acanthogorgia, bamboo corals, Chrysogorgia) and black corals (Bathypathes?). We collected a Chrysogorgia colony, a small yellow 'plexaurid' (which resembles Acanthogorgia) and a rock with a small single branch bamboo colony from the first rock pile. We headed WNW towards the 'wall' and encountered a series of rocks (sonar showed more), each with a few coral colonies: bamboos, Anthomastus, black coral, Acanthogorgia, small yellow plexaurid. Highlight imagery was collected at the rock features, then the ROV continued WNW. Continuing to the NE along the 950 m contour, we encountered some Nezumia and other rattails. At 2139 UTC, the seas were building and we were told 20 more minutes left to the dive. While several Acanthogorgia were collected into quivers, attempts were made to collect the yellow plexaurid, but the ROV was pulled off the area and the collection was aborted. The Niskin bottles were fired and the ROV was recovered. **CTD-15** was acquired before the weather became too rough for any over the side work.

April 26

Weather picked up, transit mapped Cape Fear, Blake Ridge areas, but data quality are questionable because the sea state was too rough for good acquisition. Conditions continued to be rough throughout the day and no other ops were possible, except for securing gear, catching up on sample processing, Bingo, and sleep.

April 27

We conducted a **CTD-16** at Blake Ridge seep while waiting on the sea state to mellow in order to dive. During the cast, the ship drifted ~2.5km to the east, so the USBL pole was recovered so we could transit and get on station quickly. **J2-1136** was launched at ~1600 local at Blake Ridge Seep, with a target depth of 2166m. We reached bottom at 2144 UTC at 2164m. The overall plan was to target an area of Blake Seep that had been dived on before, where we could target community collections of mussels and possibly clams, collect sediment cores within mats and adjacent to mussel beds, slurp bacterial mats, sample carbonates and water, and image hydrate. Within the first hour of the dive, we came upon a familiar scene of bucket lid markers (#3) and Bob Carney's old bucket of rabbit food and oyster shells. His name was still clearly visible on the outside of the bucket. In addition, we saw some old Alvin drop weights heavily corroded. Bob's experiment was planted in the middle of an extensive mussel bed (*B. heckeriae*) with mussels of various lengths. There were some great locations for mussel pot collections, and pots were collected in 3 different mussel patch sizes: small, medium, and large. Targeted mussel collections for various analyses also included communities found within different sized patches, and associated holothurians (cf. *chirodota*). These scoops of mussels proved to be very tricky, due to the varying mussel sizes, but several different patches were collected. Lots of dead clam shells were observed, but no large live clams were collected. However, following ROV recovery, several small clams were

present within the mussel collections. Push cores were also collected in mat environments, along with some urchins within the same area. At 0046, we crossed bucket marker #4 near a patch of mostly large *B. heckerae*. We saw a *Bathysaurus* and an *Antimora* with a parasite attached. While transiting to WP4, we came upon an enormous mound. On the bathymetry, we had a target marked hydrate, and here it was (0200UTC)! A huge hydrate mound with cave like features where two *Gaidropsarus* fish were hanging out. We collected some imagery at the mound, bubbles, and surrounding environment. Many of the rocks observed were either too big or not pliable/breakable, but we were able to collect a rock after all (0258UTC). We found a black coral attached to a mussel shell, so we collected it (2165m). Above a dense mussel bed and adjacent to the large hydrate mound, we tripped the 4 niskins. Several of the mussels were coated in white, fluffy material, not exactly like filamentous mat, similar to what has been observed at the mussel beds to the north (e.g., Norfolk seeps). During the last part of the dive, we encountered a few octopuses in and around the mussels.

April 28

At 0625, a ground fault occurred while the ROV was on bottom, so once power was restored, the ROV came off bottom. Once the ROV was recovered and on deck ~0430, the Jason team used the surface interval to try and track down the source of the fault, which is the same one that has occurred on previous dives. We transited to Cape Fear to conduct **CTD-17** to 2600m at 0800 local. The ROV **J2-1137** was launched at 1200 (local) for a dive at Cape Fear seep to ~ 2600m for a 12 hour dive. At 1816 UTC, we reached bottom at ~2587m and transited to WP1. Moderate to heavy marine snow was observed, and the seafloor was composed of fine sediment with lots of visible bioturbation and brittle stars. A drift test revealed that the bottom current was fairly swift at ~0.9kt to 160o. Small colonies of “*Anthomastus*” were observed, so one was collected early on in the dive. Extensive mat was also observed, good for push core collections and slurp sampling. The ROV moved through the WP at a decent pace, transiting through to WP3 by 2000 UTC. We continued to see and sample bacterial mats in various patch sizes, holothurians, and euplectellid sponges. The ROV was definitely being pushed around by the current and sediment scour was observed on the mud. During the dive, several bamboo colonies were observed and a few were collected. Continuing on to WP5, the current was still very strong and there was lots of particulate organic matter in the water column. Other animals observed included *Chrysogorgia*, gastropods, *Umbellula*, ophiuroids, and holothurian trails, plus patches of dead sargassum. At ~2241 we observed some odd burrow/rock mud formations and collected some rocks for characterization. The slope was sedimented interspersed with rocky outcrop features. At 0000, we found a beautiful colony of a “*Paragorgia*” and collected some imagery before sampling a snip. During the latter part of the dive, several xenophyophores were observed. The seafloor features were similar in composition to seamounts to the north, with patches of exposed rock and

xenophyophores present on the sediment. AT 0112, we imaged a very large mound feature with tubular concretions, cemented in place (D=2570m). We poked at the rocky ledges and the material appeared very clayey, and broke away easily. Toward the end of the dive, a few more push cores were collected in “background” sediments and the niskins were collected above a rocky feature with some Chrysogorgia colonies. None of the areas observed had dense coral cover nor were they very seepy. At 0220 the ROV was off bottom and headed to the surface. Overall, a very interesting dive, with lots of bacterial mats, strange tubular geological features, and corals!

April 29

We transited to Richardson West for one final CTD cast and dive before heading to the sea buoy. During the **CTD-18** on arrival (~1030), there was an issue with the con file which delayed the deployment. Following the cast, we launched the ROV (**J2-1138**) at 1330, with an approximate bottom depth of 727 m. On bottom time was 1855 UTC. The rocky seafloor appeared black, with high amounts of coral rubble and small patches of live *Enallopsammia*, *Plumarella*, white plexaurids, other octocorals, and sponges. Crusty features had dense corals growing with on the edges of ledges (several different species observed, including *Lophelia*, *Enallopsammia*). Several collections occurred within the first 4 hours of the dive, including plexaurids, primnoids, *Enallopsammia*, *Plumarella*, cf. *Leiopathes*, and crinoids. Push cores were attempted but the sediment was only a fine veneer over hard pavement. Several large *Leiopathes* were observed throughout the dive. At ~660 m near WP3, we stopped to image the ledges and collect a coral pot a mixture of live and dead *Lophelia*. There was a great deal of difficulty with the wire angle due to the swift surface current, so after a few hours of collections, the dive transitioned to a observation only dive in order to make way and minimize impact on the wire. This mode enabled the ship to maintain heading and provided an opportunity to cover a great deal of ground and observe the transition from rocky ledges and boulders to pavement with many coral colonies. During the last 3 hours of the dive, Tito took over flying and Mario was on the manipulators so we were able to fly and sample. This allowed us to trip the niskins, collect more corals, and some rock samples. Several fish species were also observed in the latter part of the dive including *Nezumia*, *Chanax* (good imagery), many *Hoplostethus*, and some type of eel, maybe synaphobranchids. We left bottom at 0306 (UTC). Good dive overall, despite the operational limitations. Some of the largest *Leiopathes* colonies from all the DEEP SEARCH dives were observed at this site.

April 30:

At ~0000 we headed to sea buoy for a 1200 arrival at the pier.

Scientific Personnel Participating

1. Erik Cordes - Associate Professor, Temple University

2. Amanda Demopoulos - Research Benthic Ecologist, U.S. Geological Survey
3. Alexis Weinnig - PhD Candidate, Temple University
4. Ryan Gasbarro - PhD Candidate, Temple University
5. Abby Keller - Research Assistant, Temple University
6. Jason Chaytor - Research Geologist, U.S. Geological Survey, Sediments Laboratory.
7. Christina A. Kellogg - Research Microbiologist, U.S. Geological Survey
8. Jennifer McClain-Counts - Biologist, U.S. Geological Survey
9. Nancy Prouty - Oceanographer, U.S. Geological Survey, coral ecosystems.
10. Cheryl Morrison - Research Geneticist, U.S. Geological Survey
11. Aaron Aunins - Biologist, U.S. Geological Survey
12. Jill Bourque - Marine Benthic Ecologist, U.S. Geological Survey
13. Jonathan Quigley - Engineering Technician, U.S. Geological Survey
14. Brian Andrews - Geographer, U.S. Geological Survey
15. Allyson Boggess - Geologist, U.S. Geological Survey
16. Michael Rasser – Marine Ecologist, Bureau of Ocean Energy Management
17. Kate Segarra - Marine Biology, Bureau of Ocean Energy Management
18. Dylan Wilford - Masters Student, University of New Hampshire
19. Furu Mienis - Research Scientist, NIOZ - Royal Netherlands Institute for Sea Research
20. Sofia Ledin - PhD Candidate, NIOZ - Royal Netherlands Institute for Sea Research
21. Chrlotte Kollman - Graduate Student, Coastal Carolina University
22. Hannah Choi - PhD Student, University of Georgia
23. Josh Parris - Research Technician, University of Georgia
24. Zachary Marinelli - Research Technician, University of Georgia
25. Caitlin Adams - Operations Coordinator, NOAA Office of Ocean Exploration and Research
26. Sandra Brooke - Associate Research Faculty, Florida State University Coastal and Marine Lab
27. Andea Quattrini - Postdoctoral Researcher, Harvey Mudd College
28. Ivan Hurzeler - Filmmaker

Master Sample Sheet

A Master Sample sheet is presented in **Appendix A**.

Plans of the Day (PODs)

A compilation Plans of the Day is presented in **Appendix B**.

Dive Plans

All the dive plans from the cruise are presented in **Appendix C**.

Jason Dive Summaries

The dive summaries from the Jason group are presented in **Appendix D**.

Appendix A. - Master Sample Sheet

RB1903 Master Sample Sheet

Sample Number	Dive.CTD.Multicore.Number	Site	Date_Collected	time	Latitude_OLD	Longitude_OLD	Depth.m.	Tentative_ID	Confirmed_ID	Erik Cordes					Chris Kellogg			Cheryl		
										Cordes.Number	LN2	ETOH	Voucher.Dfied	Live	X500.ml.bottle	LN2.1	RNALater	DNA.RNA.Shield	Bacterial.Culture Plates.From.Tissue	CM.
202	RB1903_CTD05_N04	CTD05	Richardson Hills	April 13th, 2019	14:30:00	31 59.0998	77 24.5122	737	Water	NA										
203	RB1903_CTD05_N05	CTD05	Richardson Hills	April 13th, 2019	14:30:00	31 59.0998	77 24.5122	737	Water	NA										
204	RB1903_CTD05_N06	CTD05	Richardson Hills	April 13th, 2019	14:30:00	31 59.0998	77 24.5122	737	Water	NA										
205	RB1903_CTD05_N07	CTD05	Richardson Hills	April 13th, 2019	14:30:00	31 59.0998	77 24.5122	737	Water	NA										
206	RB1903_CTD05_N08	CTD05	Richardson Hills	April 13th, 2019	14:30:00	31 59.0998	77 24.5122	737	Water	NA										
207	RB1903_CTD05_N09	CTD05	Richardson Hills	April 13th, 2019	14:30:00	31 59.0998	77 24.5122	737	Water	NA										
208	RB1903_CTD05_N10	CTD05	Richardson Hills	April 13th, 2019	14:30:00	31 59.0998	77 24.5122	737	Water	NA										
209	RB1903_CTD05_N11	CTD05	Richardson Hills	April 13th, 2019	14:30:00	31 59.0998	77 24.5122	737	Water	NA										
210	RB1903_CTD05_N12	CTD05	Richardson Hills	April 13th, 2019	14:30:00	31 59.0998	77 24.5122	737	Water	NA										
211	RB1903_CTD05_N13	CTD05	Richardson Hills	April 13th, 2019	14:30:00	31 59.0998	77 24.5122	737	Water	NA										
212	RB1903_CTD05_N14	CTD05	Richardson Hills	April 13th, 2019	14:30:00	31 59.0998	77 24.5122	737	Water	NA										
213	RB1903_CTD05_N15	CTD05	Richardson Hills	April 13th, 2019	14:30:00	31 59.0998	77 24.5122	737	Water	NA										
214	RB1903_CTD05_N16	CTD05	Richardson Hills	April 13th, 2019	14:30:00	31 59.0998	77 24.5122	737	Water	NA										
215	RB1903_CTD05_N17	CTD05	Richardson Hills	April 13th, 2019	14:30:00	31 59.0998	77 24.5122	737	Water	NA										
216	RB1903_CTD05_N18	CTD05	Richardson Hills	April 13th, 2019	14:30:00	31 59.0998	77 24.5122	737	Water	NA										
217	RB1903_CTD05_N19	CTD05	Richardson Hills	April 13th, 2019	14:30:00	31 59.0998	77 24.5122	737	Water	NA										
218	RB1903_CTD05_N20	CTD05	Richardson Hills	April 13th, 2019	14:30:00	31 59.0998	77 24.5122	737	Water	NA										
219	RB1903_CTD05_N21	CTD05	Richardson Hills	April 13th, 2019	14:30:00	31 59.0998	77 24.5122	737	Water	NA										
220	RB1903_CTD05_N22	CTD05	Richardson Hills	April 13th, 2019	14:30:00	31 59.0998	77 24.5122	737	Water	NA										
221	RB1903_CTD05_N23	CTD05	Richardson Hills	April 13th, 2019	14:30:00	31 59.0998	77 24.5122	Surface	Water	NA										
222	RB1903_CTD05_N24	CTD05	Richardson Hills	April 13th, 2019	14:30:00	31 59.0998	77 24.5122	Surface	Water	NA										
223	RB1903_CTD06_N01	CTD06	Richardson Hills	April 13th, 2019	16:30:00	31 59.4825	77 23.8062	774	Water	NA	EC9873			NA	x					x
224	RB1903_CTD06_N02	CTD06	Richardson Hills	April 13th, 2019	16:30:00	31 59.4825	77 23.8062	774	Water	NA				NA						x
225	RB1903_CTD06_N03	CTD06	Richardson Hills	April 13th, 2019	16:30:00	31 59.4825	77 23.8062	774	Water	NA				NA						x
226	RB1903_CTD06_N04	CTD06	Richardson Hills	April 13th, 2019	16:30:00	31 59.4825	77 23.8062	702	Water	NA	EC9874			NA	x					x
227	RB1903_CTD06_N05	CTD06	Richardson Hills	April 13th, 2019	16:30:00	31 59.4825	77 23.8062	702	Water	NA				NA						x
228	RB1903_CTD06_N06	CTD06	Richardson Hills	April 13th, 2019	16:30:00	31 59.4825	77 23.8062	702	Water	NA				NA						x
229	RB1903_CTD06_N07	CTD06	Richardson Hills	April 13th, 2019	16:30:00	31 59.4825	77 23.8062	559	Water	NA	EC9875			NA	x					x
230	RB1903_CTD06_N08	CTD06	Richardson Hills	April 13th, 2019	16:30:00	31 59.4825	77 23.8062	559	Water	NA				NA						x
231	RB1903_CTD06_N09	CTD06	Richardson Hills	April 13th, 2019	16:30:00	31 59.4825	77 23.8062	559	Water	NA				NA						x
232	RB1903_CTD06_N10	CTD06	Richardson Hills	April 13th, 2019	16:30:00	31 59.4825	77 23.8062	399	Water	NA	EC9876			NA	x					x
233	RB1903_CTD06_N11	CTD06	Richardson Hills	April 13th, 2019	16:30:00	31 59.4825	77 23.8062	399	Water	NA				NA						x
234	RB1903_CTD06_N12	CTD06	Richardson Hills	April 13th, 2019	16:30:00	31 59.4825	77 23.8062	399	Water	NA				NA						x
235	RB1903_CTD06_N13	CTD06	Richardson Hills	April 13th, 2019	16:30:00	31 59.4825	77 23.8062	299	Water	NA	EC9877			NA	x					
236	RB1903_CTD06_N14	CTD06	Richardson Hills	April 13th, 2019	16:30:00	31 59.4825	77 23.8062	299	Water	NA				NA						
237	RB1903_CTD06_N15	CTD06	Richardson Hills	April 13th, 2019	16:30:00	31 59.4825	77 23.8062	299	Water	NA				NA						
238	RB1903_CTD06_N16	CTD06	Richardson Hills	April 13th, 2019	16:30:00	31 59.4825	77 23.8062	200	Water	NA				NA						
239	RB1903_CTD06_N17	CTD06	Richardson Hills	April 13th, 2019	16:30:00	31 59.4825	77 23.8062	200	Water	NA	EC9878			NA	x					
240	RB1903_CTD06_N18	CTD06	Richardson Hills	April 13th, 2019	16:30:00	31 59.4825	77 23.8062	200	Water	NA				NA						
241	RB1903_CTD06_N19	CTD06	Richardson Hills	April 13th, 2019	16:30:00	31 59.4825	77 23.8062	101	Water	NA				NA						
242	RB1903_CTD06_N20	CTD06	Richardson Hills	April 13th, 2019	16:30:00	31 59.4825	77 23.8062	101	Water	NA	EC9879			NA	x					
243	RB1903_CTD06_N21	CTD06	Richardson Hills	April 13th, 2019	16:30:00	31 59.4825	77 23.8062	101	Water	NA				NA						
244	RB1903_CTD06_N22	CTD06	Richardson Hills	April 13th, 2019	16:30:00	31 59.4825	77 23.8062	5	Water	NA				NA						x
245	RB1903_CTD06_N23	CTD06	Richardson Hills	April 13th, 2019	16:30:00	31 59.4825	77 23.8062	5	Water	NA	EC9880			NA	x					x
246	RB1903_CTD06_N24	CTD06	Richardson Hills	April 13th, 2019	16:30:00	31 59.4825	77 23.8062	5	Water	NA				NA						x
247	RB1903_CTD07_N01	CTD07	Richardson Hills	April 13th, 2019	20:11:00	31 56.53	77 29.37	821	Water	NA				NA						
248	RB1903_CTD07_N02	CTD07	Richardson Hills	April 13th, 2019	20:11:00	31 56.53	77 29.37	821	Water	NA				NA						
249	RB1903_CTD07_N03	CTD07	Richardson Hills	April 13th, 2019	20:11:00	31 56.53	77 29.37	821	Water	NA	EC9881			NA	x					
250	RB1903_CTD07_N04	CTD07	Richardson Hills	April 13th, 2019	20:11:00	31 56.53	77 29.37	821	Water	NA				NA						
251	RB1903_CTD07_N05	CTD07	Richardson Hills	April 13th, 2019	20:11:00	31 56.53	77 29.37	821	Water	NA				NA						
252	RB1903_CTD07_N06	CTD07	Richardson Hills	April 13th, 2019	20:11:00	31 56.53	77 29.37	821	Water	NA				NA						
253	RB1903_CTD07_N07	CTD07	Richardson Hills	April 13th, 2019	20:11:00	31 56.53	77 29.37	821	Water	NA				NA						
254	RB1903_CTD07_N08	CTD07	Richardson Hills	April 13th, 2019	20:11:00	31 56.53	77 29.37	750	Water	NA	EC9882			NA	x					
255	RB1903_CTD07_N09	CTD07	Richardson Hills	April 13th, 2019	20:11:00	31 56.53	77 29.37	649	Water	NA	EC9883			NA	x					
256	RB1903_CTD07_N10	CTD07	Richardson Hills	April 13th, 2019	20:11:00	31 56.53	77 29.37	551	Water	NA	EC9884			NA	x					
257	RB1903_CTD07_N11	CTD07	Richardson Hills	April 13th, 2019	20:11:00	31 56.53	77 29.37	449	Water	NA	EC9885			NA	x					
258	RB1903_CTD07_N12	CTD07	Richardson Hills	April 13th, 2019	20:11:00	31 56.53	77 29.37	349	Water	NA	EC9886			NA	x					
259	RB1903_CTD07_N13	CTD07	Richardson Hills	April 13th, 2019	20:11:00	31 56.53	77 29.37	250	Water	NA	EC9887			NA	x					
260	RB1903_CTD07_N14	CTD07	Richardson Hills	April 13th, 2019	20:11:00	31 56.53	77 29.37	100	Water	NA	EC9888			NA	x					
261	RB1903_CTD07_N15	CTD07	Richardson Hills	April 13th, 2019	20:11:00	31 56.53	77 29.37	100	Water	NA				NA						
262	RB1903_CTD07_N16	CTD07	Richardson Hills	April 13th, 2019	20:11:00	31 56.53	77 29.37	100	Water	NA				NA						
263	RB1903_CTD07_N17	CTD07	Richardson Hills	April 13th, 2019	20:11:00	31 56.53	77 29.37	100	Water	NA				NA						
264	RB1903_CTD07_N18	CTD07	Richardson Hills	April 13th, 2019	20:11:00	31 56.53	77 29.37	100	Water	NA				NA						
265	RB1903_CTD07_N19	CTD07	Richardson Hills	April 13th, 2019	20:11:00	31 56.53	77 29.37	Surface	Water	NA				NA						
266	RB1903_CTD07_N20	CTD07	Richardson Hills	April 13th, 2019	20:11:00	31 56.53	77 29.37	Surface	Water	NA				NA						
267	RB1903_CTD07_N21	CTD07	Richardson Hills	April 13th, 2019	20:11:00	31 56.53	77 29.37	Surface	Water	NA	EC9889			NA	x					
268	RB1903_CTD07_N22	CTD07	Richardson Hills	April 13th, 2019	20:11:00	31 56.53	77 29.37	Surface	Water	NA				NA						

RB1903 Master Sample Sheet

Sandra Brooke				Amanda Demopoulos				Andrea Quattrini		Nancy Prouty			Mandy Joye		Jason Chaytor			Mienis			Close											
Live for Growth Experiment	Live.1	Formalin.10.	LN2.3	RB1903.2019..	Formalin.10.1	ETOH.2	Frozen.at.20	RB1903.19..	X95.ETOH	X70..ETOH	Mud.Sample	Water.Sample	In.foli...20.C.	shells.rocks.skeleton	Mud.Sample.1	Water.Sample.1	Sediment.Chem	Fridge	Dried.Geology	Water.Sample.2	Skeleton.Sample	Water.Sample.3	id	date	lat_RENAV	long_RENAV	depth	heading	pitch	roll	altitude	
NA													x				NA	NA					1140	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	
NA																	NA	NA					1141	4/24/2019	35.92604177	-74.80534243	-436.966	34.92	1.47	2.45	1.5	
NA																	NA	NA					1142	4/24/2019	35.92604177	-74.80534243	-436.966	34.92	1.47	2.45	1.5	
NA																	NA	NA					1143	4/24/2019	35.92604177	-74.80534243	-436.966	34.92	1.47	2.45	1.5	
NA																	NA	NA					1144	4/24/2019	35.9277822	-74.80808279	-395.257	66.162	-7.439	1.103	2.1	
NA																	NA	NA					1145	4/24/2019	35.9277822	-74.80808279	-395.257	66.162	-7.439	1.103	2.1	
NA																	NA	NA					1146	4/24/2019	35.9277822	-74.80808279	-395.257	66.162	-7.439	1.103	2.1	
NA																	NA	NA					1147	4/24/2019	35.9277822	-74.80808279	-395.257	66.162	-7.439	1.103	2.1	
NA														x			NA	NA					1148	4/24/2019	35.9277822	-74.80808279	-395.257	66.162	-7.439	1.103	2.1	
NA														x			NA	NA					1149	4/24/2019	35.92776708	-74.80809286	-396.17	17.249	-1.97	-2.731	2	
NA														x			NA	NA					1150	4/24/2019	35.9341819	-74.81746564	-235.025	305.12	-8.1	2.37	1.2	
NA														x			NA	NA					1151	4/24/2019	35.93417842	-74.81744344	-235.088	305.657	-8.29	1.831	1.2	
NA									x								NA	NA					1152	4/24/2019	35.93417842	-74.81744344	-235.088	305.657	-8.29	1.831	1.2	
NA														x			NA	NA					1153	4/24/2019	35.93604895	-74.81818482	-210.098	87.94	-3.34	5.656	0.9	
NA																	NA	NA					1154	4/24/2019	35.93532111	-74.81789603	-220.037	180.81	-7.33	3.275	0.8	
NA														x			NA	NA					1155	4/24/2019	35.92604543	-74.80533998	-436.263	31.93	-8.743	2.162	3.1	
NA									x								NA	NA					1156	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	
NA														x			NA	NA					1157	4/24/2019	35.92783144	-74.80839481	-398.995	28.27	-5.101	2.453	3.6	
NA									x								NA	NA					1158	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	
NA														x			NA	NA					1159	4/24/2019	35.9260414	-74.80534221	-436.981	34.446	1.38	2.424	1.5	
NA																	NA	NA					1160	4/24/2019	35.92573942	-74.80496592	-447.224	334.479	-3.7	1.94	2.9	
NA																	NA	NA					1161	4/24/2019	35.92574813	-74.80498861	-446.925	335.768	-2.448	0.899	2.7	
NA																	NA	NA					1162	4/24/2019	35.92574813	-74.80498861	-446.925	335.768	-2.448	0.899	2.7	
NA																	NA	NA					1163	4/24/2019	35.92575104	-74.80498972	-446.375	338.098	-4.62	1.811	3	
NA																	NA	NA					1164	4/24/2019	35.92575215	-74.80499235	-446.4	338.99	-4.509	1.793	3	
NA																	NA	NA					1165	4/24/2019	35.92575215	-74.80499235	-446.4	338.99	-4.509	1.793	3	
NA																	NA	NA					1166	4/24/2019	35.92575215	-74.80499235	-446.4	338.99	-4.509	1.793	3	
NA																	NA	NA					1167	4/24/2019	35.92575215	-74.80499235	-446.4	338.99	-4.509	1.793	3	
NA																	NA	NA					1168	4/24/2019	35.92575215	-74.80499235	-446.4	338.99	-4.509	1.793	3	
NA							x										NA	NA					1169	4/24/2019	35.92788467	-74.81202072	-336.555	270.679	-5.821	0.097	1.4	
NA							x										NA	NA					1170	4/24/2019	35.92788411	-74.81202084	-336.542	270.569	-5.76	-0.09	1.4	
NA							x										NA	NA					1171	4/24/2019	35.92788346	-74.81202114	-336.564	270.589	-5.724	0.102	1.4	
NA							x										NA	NA					1172	4/24/2019	35.92788535	-74.81202066	-336.547	270.656	-5.36	0.534	1.4	
NA																	NA	NA					1173	4/24/2019	35.92788506	-74.81202066	-336.584	270.759	-5.35	-0.296	1.3	
NA																	NA	NA					1174	4/24/2019	35.92788506	-74.81202066	-336.584	270.759	-5.35	-0.296	1.3	
NA																	NA	NA					1175	4/24/2019	35.92788553	-74.81202076	-336.555	270.69	-5.25	0.069	1.3	
NA																	NA	NA					1176	4/24/2019	35.92788571	-74.81202083	-336.57	270.72	-5.32	0.36	1.4	
NA																	NA	NA					1177	4/24/2019	35.93481584	-74.81770533	-227.574	273.62	-6.92	-0.46	1.1	
NA																	NA	NA					1178	4/24/2019	35.93481607	-74.8177066	-227.553	273.59	-6.97	-0.56	1.1	
NA																	NA	NA					1179	4/24/2019	35.93481642	-74.81770682	-227.566	273.58	-7	-0.61	1.1	
NA																	NA	NA					1180	4/24/2019	35.93542944	-74.817194	-218.275	81.03	-1.434	5.13	0.9	
NA																	NA	NA					1181	4/24/2019	35.93543052	-74.81719297	-218.282	81.026	-1.22	5.15	0.8	
NA																	NA	NA					1182	4/24/2019	35.9348159	-74.81770449	-227.535	273.636	-6.888	-0.086	1.1	
NA																	NA	NA					1183	4/24/2019	35.9354279	-74.81719373	-218.278	81.18	-1.23	5.23	0.8	
NA																	NA	NA					1184	4/24/2019	35.93481584	-74.81770379	-227.531	273.612	-6.89	0.038	1.1	
NA																	NA	NA					1185	4/24/2019	35.93542754	-74.81719331	-218.254	81.22	-1.28	5.23	0.9	
NA																	NA	NA					1186	4/24/2019	35.93542992	-74.81719378	-218.247	81.1	-1.16	5.226	0.8	
NA																	NA	NA					1187	4/24/2019	35.93481381	-74.81770559	-227.532	273.638	-6.79	0.012	1.1	
NA																	NA	NA					1188	4/24/2019	35.92787473	-74.81213982	-334.922	296.66	-6.22	2.49	1.7	
NA																	NA	NA					1189	4/24/2019	35.93481474	-74.81770427	-227.512	273.62	-6.842	-0.17	1.1	
NA																	NA	NA					1190	4/24/2019	35.93543064	-74.81719178	-218.254	80.91	-1.36	4.97	0.9	
NA																	NA	NA					1191	4/24/2019	35.93543049	-74.81719101	-218.254	80.7	-1.15	5.16	0.8	
NA																	NA	NA					1192	4/24/2019	35.92787359	-74.81213929	-334.938	296.27	-6.15	2.21	1.7	
NA																	NA	NA					1193	4/24/2019	35.93481437	-74.81770477	-227.526	273.63	-6.79	-0.23	1.1	
NA																	NA	NA					1194	4/24/2019	35.92787146	-74.81213843	-334.906	295.544	-6.749	2.184	1.7	
NA																	NA	NA					1195	4/24/2019	35.92787218	-74.81213868	-334.933	295.78	-6.574	2.274	1.7	
NA																	NA	NA					1196	4/24/2019	35.92787282	-74.81213896	-334.932	296.09	-6.411	2.36	1.7	
NA																	NA	NA					1197	4/24/2019	35.92787006	-74.8121386						

RB1903 Master Sample Sheet

Sandra Brooke			Amanda Demopoulos				Andrea Quattrini			Nancy Prouty			Mandy Joye		Jason Chaytor			Mienis		Close												
Live.for.Growth Experiment	Live.1	Formalin.10.	LN2.3	RB1903.2019..	Formalin.10..1	ETOH.2	Frozen.at..20	RB1903.19..	X95.ETOH	X70..ETOH	Mud.Sample	Water.Sample	in.foli...20.C.	shells.rocks.skeleton	Mud.Sample.1	Water.Sample.1	Sediment.Chem	Fridge	Dried.Geology	Water.Sample.2	Skeleton.Sample	Water.Sample.3	id	date	lat_RENAV	long_RENAV	depth	heading	pitch	roll	altitude	
NA								RB-19-110	x								NA	NA					1207	4/25/2019	33.91663762	-75.8340563	-976.906	334.917	-4.668	7.763	2.2	
NA														x			NA	NA					1208	4/25/2019	33.91663762	-75.8340563	-976.906	334.917	-4.668	7.763	2.2	
NA	x							RB-19-111	x								NA	NA					1209	4/25/2019	33.91891361	-75.83344058	-944.771	0.646	-0.804	7.44	1.6	
NA																	NA	NA					1210	4/25/2019	33.91891361	-75.83344058	-944.771	0.646	-0.804	7.44	1.6	
NA																	NA	NA					1211	4/25/2019	33.91891361	-75.83344058	-944.771	0.646	-0.804	7.44	1.6	
NA																	NA	NA					1212	4/25/2019	33.91891361	-75.83344058	-944.771	0.646	-0.804	7.44	1.6	
NA																	NA	NA					1213	4/25/2019	33.91891361	-75.83344058	-944.771	0.646	-0.804	7.44	1.6	
NA																	NA	NA					1214	4/25/2019	33.91891361	-75.83344058	-944.771	0.646	-0.804	7.44	1.6	
NA	x							RB-19-112	x								NA	NA					1215	4/25/2019	33.91751441	-75.83403471	-959.614	299.43	-7.167	0.854	3.3	
NA										x							NA	NA					1216	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
NA											x						NA	NA					1217	4/25/2019	33.91892749	-75.8333108	-947.833	4.234	-6.135	4.175	1.8	
NA												x					NA	NA					1218	4/25/2019	33.91892749	-75.8333108	-947.833	4.234	-6.135	4.175	1.8	
NA																	NA	NA					1219	4/25/2019	33.91892749	-75.8333108	-947.833	4.234	-6.135	4.175	1.8	
NA																	NA	NA					1220	4/25/2019	33.91892749	-75.8333108	-947.833	4.234	-6.135	4.175	1.8	
NA																	NA	NA					1221	4/25/2019	33.91579585	-75.8318424	-1027.369	317.62	-2.262	2.8	1.4	
NA																	NA	NA					1222	4/25/2019	33.91579533	-75.8318421	-1027.357	317.63	-2.728	2.772	1.5	
NA															x		NA	NA					1223	4/25/2019	33.91579533	-75.8318421	-1027.357	317.63	-2.728	2.772	1.5	
NA															x		NA	NA					1224	4/25/2019	33.91579732	-75.83184286	-1027.388	317.51	-2.452	2.88	1.5	
NA										x							NA	NA					1225	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
NA										x							NA	NA					1226	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
NA										x							NA	NA					1227	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
NA										x							NA	NA					1228	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
NA										x							NA	NA					1229	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
NA							x										NA	NA					1230	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
NA							x										NA	NA					1231	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
NA															x		NA	NA					1232	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
NA															x		NA	NA					1233	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
NA															x		NA	NA					1234	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
NA															x		NA	NA					1235	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
NA															x		NA	NA					1236	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
NA															x		NA	NA					1237	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
NA															x		NA	NA					1238	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
NA															x		NA	NA					1239	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
NA															x		NA	NA					1240	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
NA															x		NA	NA					1241	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
NA															x		NA	NA					1242	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
NA										x							NA	NA					1243	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
NA															x		NA	NA					1244	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
NA																	NA	NA					1245	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
NA																	NA	NA					1246	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
NA																	NA	NA					1247	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
NA																	NA	NA					1248	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
NA																	NA	NA					1249	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
NA																	NA	NA					1250	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
NA																	NA	NA					1251	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
NA																	NA	NA					1252	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
NA																	NA	NA					1253	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
NA																	NA	NA					1254	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
NA																	NA	NA					1255	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
NA																	NA	NA					1256	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
NA																	NA	NA					1257	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
NA																	NA	NA					1258	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
NA																	NA	NA					1259	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
NA																	NA	NA					1260	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
NA																	NA	NA					1261	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
NA																	NA	NA					1262	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
NA																	NA	NA					1263	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
NA																	NA	NA					1264	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
NA																	NA	NA					1265	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
NA																	NA	NA					1266	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
NA																	NA	NA					1267	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
NA																	NA	NA					1268	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
NA																	NA	NA					1269	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
NA																	NA	NA					1270	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
NA																	NA	NA					1271	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
NA																	NA	NA					1272	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
NA																	NA	NA					1273	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA				

RB1903 Master Sample Sheet

Sandra Brooke			Amanda Demopoulos				Andrea Quattrini		Nancy Prouty			Mandy Joye		Jason Chaytor			Mienis		Close												
Live (or Growth Experiment)	Live.1	Formalin.10.	LN2.3	RB1903.2019..	Formalin.10.1	ETOH.2	Frozen.at.20	RB1903.19.	X95.ETOH	X70.ETOH	Mud.Sample	Water.Sample	in.foli...20.C.	shells.rocks.skeleton	Mud.Sample.1	Water.Sample.1	Sediment.Chem	Fridge	Dried.Geology	Water.Sample.2	Skeleton.Sample	Water.Sample.3	id	date	lat_RENAV	long_RENAV	depth	heading	pitch	roll	altitude
NA		x						RB-19-156	x								NA	NA					1341	4/28/2019	32.49364462	-76.19095629	-2166.497	36.701	-2.67	0.88	0.6
NA		x						RB-19-157	x								NA	NA					1342	4/28/2019	32.49364462	-76.19095629	-2166.497	36.701	-2.67	0.88	0.6
NA		x						RB-19-158	x								NA	NA					1343	4/28/2019	32.49364462	-76.19095629	-2166.497	36.701	-2.67	0.88	0.6
NA		x						RB-19-159	x								NA	NA					1344	4/28/2019	32.49364462	-76.19095629	-2166.497	36.701	-2.67	0.88	0.6
NA		x						RB-19-160	x								NA	NA					1345	4/28/2019	32.49364462	-76.19095629	-2166.497	36.701	-2.67	0.88	0.6
NA		x						RB-19-161	x								NA	NA					1346	4/28/2019	32.49364462	-76.19095629	-2166.497	36.701	-2.67	0.88	0.6
NA		x						RB-19-162	x								NA	NA					1347	4/28/2019	32.49364462	-76.19095629	-2166.497	36.701	-2.67	0.88	0.6
NA		x						RB-19-163	x								NA	NA					1348	4/28/2019	32.49364462	-76.19095629	-2166.497	36.701	-2.67	0.88	0.6
NA		x						RB-19-164	x								NA	NA					1349	4/28/2019	32.49364462	-76.19095629	-2166.497	36.701	-2.67	0.88	0.6
NA		x															NA	NA					1350	4/28/2019	32.49364462	-76.19095629	-2166.497	36.701	-2.67	0.88	0.6
NA		x															NA	NA					1351	4/28/2019	32.49364462	-76.19095629	-2166.497	36.701	-2.67	0.88	0.6
NA		x															NA	NA					1352	4/28/2019	32.49364462	-76.19095629	-2166.497	36.701	-2.67	0.88	0.6
NA		x															NA	NA					1353	4/28/2019	32.49364462	-76.19095629	-2166.497	36.701	-2.67	0.88	0.6
NA		x															NA	NA					1354	4/28/2019	32.49364462	-76.19095629	-2166.497	36.701	-2.67	0.88	0.6
NA		x															NA	NA					1355	4/28/2019	32.49364462	-76.19095629	-2166.497	36.701	-2.67	0.88	0.6
NA		x						RB-19-165	x								NA	NA					1356	4/28/2019	32.49364462	-76.19095629	-2166.497	36.701	-2.67	0.88	0.6
NA		x						RB-19-166	x								NA	NA					1357	4/28/2019	32.49364462	-76.19095629	-2166.497	36.701	-2.67	0.88	0.6
NA		x						RB-19-167	x								NA	NA					1358	4/28/2019	32.49364462	-76.19095629	-2166.497	36.701	-2.67	0.88	0.6
NA		x						RB-19-168	x								NA	NA					1359	4/28/2019	32.49364462	-76.19095629	-2166.497	36.701	-2.67	0.88	0.6
NA		x						RB-19-169	x								NA	NA					1360	4/28/2019	32.49364462	-76.19095629	-2166.497	36.701	-2.67	0.88	0.6
NA		x						RB-19-170	x								NA	NA					1361	4/28/2019	32.49364462	-76.19095629	-2166.497	36.701	-2.67	0.88	0.6
NA		x						RB-19-171	x								NA	NA					1362	4/28/2019	32.49364462	-76.19095629	-2166.497	36.701	-2.67	0.88	0.6
NA		x						RB-19-172	x								NA	NA					1363	4/28/2019	32.49364462	-76.19095629	-2166.497	36.701	-2.67	0.88	0.6
NA		x						RB-19-173	x								NA	NA					1364	4/28/2019	32.49364462	-76.19095629	-2166.497	36.701	-2.67	0.88	0.6
NA		x						RB-19-174	x								NA	NA					1365	4/28/2019	32.49364462	-76.19095629	-2166.497	36.701	-2.67	0.88	0.6
NA		x						RB-19-175	x								NA	NA					1366	4/28/2019	32.49364462	-76.19095629	-2166.497	36.701	-2.67	0.88	0.6
NA		x						RB-19-176	x								NA	NA					1367	4/28/2019	32.49364462	-76.19095629	-2166.497	36.701	-2.67	0.88	0.6
NA		x						RB-19-177	x								NA	NA					1368	4/28/2019	32.49364462	-76.19095629	-2166.497	36.701	-2.67	0.88	0.6
NA		x						RB-19-178	x								NA	NA					1369	4/28/2019	32.49364462	-76.19095629	-2166.497	36.701	-2.67	0.88	0.6
NA		x															NA	NA					1370	4/28/2019	32.49364462	-76.19095629	-2166.497	36.701	-2.67	0.88	0.6
NA		x															NA	NA					1371	4/28/2019	32.49364462	-76.19095629	-2166.497	36.701	-2.67	0.88	0.6
NA		x															NA	NA					1372	4/28/2019	32.49364462	-76.19095629	-2166.497	36.701	-2.67	0.88	0.6
NA																	NA	NA					1373	4/28/2019	32.49364462	-76.19095629	-2166.497	36.701	-2.67	0.88	0.6
NA																	NA	NA					1374	4/28/2019	32.49364462	-76.19095629	-2166.497	36.701	-2.67	0.88	0.6
NA																	NA	NA					1375	4/28/2019	32.49364462	-76.19095629	-2166.497	36.701	-2.67	0.88	0.6
NA																	NA	NA					1376	4/28/2019	32.49364462	-76.19095629	-2166.497	36.701	-2.67	0.88	0.6
NA																	NA	NA					1377	4/28/2019	32.49364462	-76.19095629	-2166.497	36.701	-2.67	0.88	0.6
NA																	NA	NA					1378	4/28/2019	32.49364462	-76.19095629	-2166.497	36.701	-2.67	0.88	0.6
NA																	NA	NA					1379	4/28/2019	32.49364462	-76.19095629	-2166.497	36.701	-2.67	0.88	0.6
NA																	NA	NA					1380	4/28/2019	32.49364462	-76.19095629	-2166.497	36.701	-2.67	0.88	0.6
NA																	NA	NA					1381	4/28/2019	32.49364462	-76.19095629	-2166.497	36.701	-2.67	0.88	0.6
NA																	NA	NA					1382	4/28/2019	32.49364462	-76.19095629	-2166.497	36.701	-2.67	0.88	0.6
NA																	NA	NA					1383	4/28/2019	32.49364462	-76.19095629	-2166.497	36.701	-2.67	0.88	0.6
NA																	NA	NA					1384	4/28/2019	32.49364462	-76.19095629	-2166.497	36.701	-2.67	0.88	0.6
NA																	NA	NA					1385	4/28/2019	32.49364462	-76.19095629	-2166.497	36.701	-2.67	0.88	0.6
NA																	NA	NA					1386	4/28/2019	32.49364462	-76.19095629	-2166.497	36.701	-2.67	0.88	0.6
NA		x															NA	NA					1387	4/28/2019	32.49364462	-76.19095629	-2166.497	36.701	-2.67	0.88	0.6
NA		x															NA	NA					1388	4/28/2019	32.49364462	-76.19095629	-2166.497	36.701	-2.67	0.88	0.6
NA		x															NA	NA					1389	4/28/2019	32.49364462	-76.19095629	-2166.497	36.701	-2.67	0.88	0.6
NA																	NA	NA					1390	4/28/2019	32.49364462	-76.19095629	-2166.497	36.701	-2.67	0.88	0.6
NA																	NA	NA					1391	4/28/2019	32.49364462	-76.19095629	-2166.497	36.701	-2.67	0.88	0.6
NA																	NA	NA					1392	4/28/2019	32.49364462	-76.19095629	-2166.497	36.701	-2.67	0.88	0.6
NA																	NA	NA					1393	4/28/2019	32.49364462	-76.19095629	-2166.497	36.701	-2.67	0.88	0.6
NA																	NA	NA					1394	4/28/2019	32.49364462	-76.19095629	-2166.497	36.701	-2.67	0.88	0.6
NA																	NA	NA					1395	4/28/2019	32.49364462	-76.19095629	-2166.497	36.701	-2.67	0.88	0.6
NA																	NA	NA					1396	4/28/2019	32.49364462	-76.19095629					

RB1903 Master Sample Sheet

Sandra Brooke				Amanda Demopoulos				Andrea Quattrini			Nancy Prouty				Mandy Joye		Jason Chaytor			Mienis			Close								
Live.for.Growth Experiment	Live.1	Formalin.10.	LN2.3	RB1903.2019..	Formalin.10..1	ETOH.2	Frozen.at..20	RB1903.19..	X95.ETOH	X70..ETOH	Mud.Sample	Water.Sample	in.foli...20.C.	shells.rocks.skeleton	Mud.Sample.1	Water.Sample.1	Sediment.Chem	Fridge	Dried.Geology	Water.Sample.2	Skeleton.Sample	Water.Sample.3	id	date	lat_RENAV	long_RENAV	depth	heading	pitch	roll	altitude
NA																							1408	4/28/2019	32.49364462	-76.19095629	-2166.497	36.701	-2.67	0.88	0.6
NA																							1409	4/28/2019	32.49364462	-76.19095629	-2166.497	36.701	-2.67	0.88	0.6
NA																							1410	4/28/2019	32.49364462	-76.19095629	-2166.497	36.701	-2.67	0.88	0.6
NA																							1411	4/28/2019	32.49364462	-76.19095629	-2166.497	36.701	-2.67	0.88	0.6
NA																							1412	4/28/2019	32.49364462	-76.19095629	-2166.497	36.701	-2.67	0.88	0.6
NA								RB-19-179	x														1413	4/28/2019	32.49364462	-76.19095629	-2166.497	36.701	-2.67	0.88	0.6
NA								RB-19-180	x														1414	4/28/2019	32.49364462	-76.19095629	-2166.497	36.701	-2.67	0.88	0.6
NA								RB-19-181	x														1415	4/28/2019	32.49364462	-76.19095629	-2166.497	36.701	-2.67	0.88	0.6
NA								RB-19-182	x														1416	4/28/2019	32.49364462	-76.19095629	-2166.497	36.701	-2.67	0.88	0.6
NA								RB-19-183	x														1417	4/28/2019	32.49364462	-76.19095629	-2166.497	36.701	-2.67	0.88	0.6
NA								RB-19-184	x														1418	4/28/2019	32.49364462	-76.19095629	-2166.497	36.701	-2.67	0.88	0.6
NA								RB-19-185	x														1419	4/28/2019	32.49364462	-76.19095629	-2166.497	36.701	-2.67	0.88	0.6
NA								RB-19-186	x														1420	4/28/2019	32.49364462	-76.19095629	-2166.497	36.701	-2.67	0.88	0.6
NA								RB-19-187	x														1421	4/28/2019	32.49364462	-76.19095629	-2166.497	36.701	-2.67	0.88	0.6
NA								RB-19-188	x														1422	4/28/2019	32.49364462	-76.19095629	-2166.497	36.701	-2.67	0.88	0.6
NA								RB-19-189	x														1423	4/28/2019	32.49364462	-76.19095629	-2166.497	36.701	-2.67	0.88	0.6
NA								RB-19-190	x														1424	4/28/2019	32.49364462	-76.19095629	-2166.497	36.701	-2.67	0.88	0.6
NA								RB-19-191	x														1425	4/28/2019	32.49364462	-76.19095629	-2166.497	36.701	-2.67	0.88	0.6
NA								RB-19-146	x														1426	4/28/2019	32.49364462	-76.19095629	-2166.497	36.701	-2.67	0.88	0.6
NA	x							RB-19-147	x														1427	4/28/2019	32.49393949	-76.19132766	-2167.059	336.82	-10.5	5.24	0.6
NA								RB-19-148	x														1428	4/28/2019	32.49393949	-76.19132766	-2167.059	336.82	-10.5	5.24	0.6
NA								RB-19-149	x														1429	4/28/2019	32.49393949	-76.19132766	-2167.059	336.82	-10.5	5.24	0.6
NA								RB-19-149	x														1430	4/28/2019	32.49393949	-76.19132766	-2167.059	336.82	-10.5	5.24	0.6
NA								RB-19-113	x														1431	4/28/2019	32.49393949	-76.19132766	-2167.059	336.82	-10.5	5.24	0.6
NA								RB-19-113	x														1432	4/28/2019	32.49393949	-76.19132766	-2167.059	336.82	-10.5	5.24	0.6
NA								RB-19-113	x														1433	4/28/2019	32.49386424	-76.19175148	-2166.77	169.93	-1.56	0.55	0.6
NA								RB-19-113	x														1434	4/28/2019	32.49418492	-76.19020522	-2168.934	78.14	-5.154	-0.25	0.8
NA								RB-19-113	x														1435	4/28/2019	32.49364687	-76.1911758	-2166.14	63.45	0.46	1.361	0.7
NA	x							RB-19-114	x														1436	4/28/2019	32.49366782	-76.19119384	-2166.119	63.43	0.37	1.389	0.7
NA	x							RB-19-114	x														1437	4/28/2019	32.49366782	-76.19119384	-2166.119	63.43	0.37	1.389	0.7
NA								RB-19-114	x														1438	4/28/2019	32.49366782	-76.19119384	-2166.119	63.43	0.37	1.389	0.7
NA								RB-19-114	x														1439	4/28/2019	32.49402172	-76.19069945	-2168.517	99.7	-5.191	-0.1	0.9
NA								RB-19-114	x														1440	4/28/2019	32.49402172	-76.19069945	-2168.517	99.7	-5.191	-0.1	0.9
NA								RB-19-114	x														1441	4/28/2019	32.49395778	-76.19114424	-2167.773	66.19	-5.661	5.21	1.9
NA								RB-19-114	x														1442	4/28/2019	32.49360714	-76.19090632	-2164.043	76.74	-8.47	-0.951	3.5
NA								RB-19-114	x														1443	4/28/2019	32.49360714	-76.19090632	-2164.043	76.74	-8.47	-0.951	3.5
NA								RB-19-114	x														1444	4/28/2019	32.49360714	-76.19090632	-2164.043	76.74	-8.47	-0.951	3.5
NA								RB-19-114	x														1445	4/28/2019	32.49360714	-76.19090632	-2164.043	76.74	-8.47	-0.951	3.5
NA								RB-19-114	x														1446	4/27/2019	32.49394126	-76.19093716	-2166.698	358.62	-5.86	0.727	0.8
NA								RB-19-114	x														1447	4/27/2019	32.49394126	-76.19093716	-2166.698	358.62	-5.86	0.727	0.8
NA								RB-19-114	x														1448	4/27/2019	32.49394126	-76.19093716	-2166.698	358.62	-5.86	0.727	0.8
NA								RB-19-114	x														1449	4/27/2019	32.49394126	-76.19093716	-2166.698	358.62	-5.86	0.727	0.8
NA								RB-19-114	x														1450	4/27/2019	32.49394126	-76.19093716	-2166.698	358.62	-5.86	0.727	0.8
NA								RB-19-114	x														1451	4/27/2019	32.49394126	-76.19093716	-2166.698	358.62	-5.86	0.727	0.8
NA								RB-19-114	x														1452	4/27/2019	32.49393719	-76.19092117	-2166.761	7.99	-5.15	4.25	0.6
NA								RB-19-114	x														1453	4/27/2019	32.49393719	-76.19092117	-2166.761	7.99	-5.15	4.25	0.6
NA								RB-19-114	x														1454	4/27/2019	32.49393719	-76.19092117	-2166.761	7.99	-5.15	4.25	0.6
NA								RB-19-114	x														1455	4/27/2019	32.49393719	-76.19092117	-2166.761	7.99	-5.15	4.25	0.6
NA								RB-19-114	x														1456	4/27/2019	32.49393719	-76.19092117	-2166.761	7.99	-5.15	4.25	0.6
NA								RB-19-114	x														1457	4/27/2019	32.49393719	-76.19092117	-2166.761	7.99	-5.15	4.25	0.6
NA								RB-19-114	x														1458	4/27/2019	32.49393719	-76.19092117	-2166.761	7.99	-5.15	4.25	0.6
NA								RB-19-114	x														1459	4/27/2019	32.49393719	-76.19092117	-2166.761	7.99	-5.15	4.25	0.6
NA								RB-19-114	x														1460	4/27/2019	32.49393719	-76.19092117	-2166.761	7.99	-5.15	4.25	0.6
NA								RB-19-114	x														1461	4/27/2019	32.49393719	-76.19092117	-2166.761	7.99	-5.15	4.25	0.6
NA								RB-19-114	x														1462	4/27/2019	32.49393719	-76.19092117	-2166.761	7.99	-5.15	4.25	0.6
NA								RB-19-114	x														1463	4/27/2019	32.49393719	-76.19092117	-2166.761	7.99	-5.15	4.25	0.6
NA								RB-19-114	x																						

RB1903 Master Sample Sheet

Sandra Brooke			Amanda Demopoulos				Andrea Quattrini		Nancy Prouty				Mandy Joye		Jason Chaytor			Mienis	Close													
Live (or Growth Experiment)	Live.1	Formalin.10.	LN2.3	RB1903.2019..	Formalin.10..1	ETOH.2	Frozen.at..20	RB1903.19..	X95.ETOH	X70..ETOH	Mud.Sample	Water.Sample	in.foli...20.C.	shells.rocks.skeleton	Mud.Sample.1	Water.Sample.1	Sediment.Chem	Fridge	Dried.Geology	Water.Sample.2	Skeleton.Sample	Water.Sample.3	id	date	lat_RENAV	long_RENAV	depth	heading	pitch	roll	altitude	
NA																		NA	NA				1475	4/28/2019	32.49365537	-76.19096981	-2166.441	36.7	-2.58	0.89	0.6	
NA																		NA	NA				1476	4/28/2019	32.49365537	-76.19096981	-2166.441	36.7	-2.58	0.89	0.6	
NA																		NA	NA				1477	4/27/2019	32.49393983	-76.1909275	-2166.57	0.339	-6.442	3.59	0.7	
NA																		NA	NA				1478	4/27/2019	32.49393983	-76.1909275	-2166.57	0.339	-6.442	3.59	0.7	
NA																		NA	NA				1479	4/27/2019	32.49392036	-76.19092236	-2166.588	0.333	-6.32	3.996	0.7	
NA																		NA	NA				1480	4/27/2019	32.49390642	-76.19091255	-2166.586	0.332	-6.25	4.23	0.7	
NA																		NA	NA				1481	4/27/2019	32.49391028	-76.19093022	-2166.601	0.37	-6.48	3.74	0.7	
NA																		NA	NA				1482	4/27/2019	32.4939244	-76.19092342	-2166.557	0.35	-6.42	4.01	0.7	
NA																		NA	NA				1483	4/27/2019	32.49391669	-76.19091039	-2166.602	0.34	-6.22	4.37	0.7	
NA																		NA	NA				1484	4/27/2019	32.49392108	-76.19093397	-2166.538	0.36	-6.48	3.79	0.7	
NA																		NA	NA				1485	4/28/2019	32.49493018	-76.18985468	-2168.691	10.642	-1.67	2.13	1.2	
NA																		NA	NA				1486	4/28/2019	32.49492996	-76.18986021	-2168.717	10.604	-1.55	2.16	1.2	
NA																		NA	NA				1487	4/28/2019	32.49366265	-76.19116675	-2166.135	63.341	-0.049	1.391	0.7	
NA																		NA	NA				1488	4/28/2019	32.49491374	-76.18984952	-2168.729	10.603	-1.431	2.15	1.2	
NA																		NA	NA				1489	4/28/2019	32.49492557	-76.18985866	-2168.709	10.558	-1.429	2.15	1.2	
NA																		NA	NA				1490	4/28/2019	32.4949264	-76.18985236	-2168.724	10.62	-1.533	2.16	1.2	
NA																		NA	NA				1491	4/28/2019	32.49491687	-76.18985291	-2168.731	10.58	-1.38	2.16	1.2	
NA																		NA	NA				1492	4/28/2019	32.49492193	-76.18985253	-2168.695	10.569	-1.43	2.169	1.2	
NA																		NA	NA				1493	4/28/2019	32.49366027	-76.19117111	-2166.122	63.389	-0.171	1.43	0.7	
NA																		NA	NA				1494	4/28/2019	32.49491985	-76.18985503	-2168.724	10.54	-1.44	2.14	1.2	
NA																		NA	NA				1495	4/27/2019	32.49366344	-76.19119099	-2166.16	63.44	-0.17	1.45	0.7	
NA																		NA	NA				1496	4/28/2019	32.49366186	-76.19118183	-2166.135	63.41	-0.13	1.43	0.7	
NA																		NA	NA				1497	4/28/2019	32.49366765	-76.19118824	-2166.137	63.41	-0.12	1.48	0.7	
NA																		NA	NA				1498	4/28/2019	32.49366183	-76.19118375	-2166.129	63.42	-0.223	1.501	0.7	
NA																		NA	NA				1499	4/28/2019	32.49367029	-76.19118476	-2166.143	63.397	-0.063	1.47	0.7	
NA																		NA	NA				1500	4/28/2019	32.4936583	-76.19118452	-2166.112	63.377	-0.13	1.44	0.7	
NA																		NA	NA				1501	4/28/2019	32.49365025	-76.19095962	-2166.44	36.73	-2.46	0.82	0.6	
NA													x					NA	NA				1502	4/27/2019	32.49396374	-76.19093337	-2166.7	358.83	-5.69	1.15	0.7	
NA								RB-19-192	x									NA	NA				1503	4/28/2019	32.97959626	-75.92844852	-2589.669	12.08	-2.54	4.09	0.9	
NA								RB-19-193	x									NA	NA				1504	4/28/2019	32.97423129	-75.91799423	-2608.112	127.871	-4.086	-0.3	1.4	
NA								RB-19-194	x									NA	NA				1505	4/28/2019	32.97423129	-75.91799423	-2608.112	127.871	-4.086	-0.3	1.4	
NA																		NA	NA				1506	4/29/2019	32.97320195	-75.9154219	-2592.2	16.816	4.817	-4.26	1.1	
NA																		NA	NA				1507	4/29/2019	32.97320195	-75.9154219	-2592.2	16.816	4.817	-4.26	1.1	
NA								RB-19-195	x									NA	NA				1508	4/28/2019	32.97833978	-75.92369746	-2600.519	34.649	-6.37	4.66	1	
NA								RB-19-196	x									NA	NA				1509	4/29/2019	32.97328838	-75.91554172	-2594.065	336.01	-3.589	-7.357	1.2	
NA																		NA	NA				1510	4/29/2019	32.97328838	-75.91554172	-2594.065	336.01	-3.589	-7.357	1.2	
NA																		NA	NA				1511	4/28/2019	32.97945482	-75.92658919	-2593.157	57.289	-7.6	4.313	1.2	
NA																		NA	NA				1512	4/28/2019	32.97967189	-75.92827192	-2590.769	6.64	-3.26	4.11	0.9	
NA																		NA	NA				1513	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
NA																		NA	NA				1514	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
NA																		NA	NA				1515	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
NA																		NA	NA				1516	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
NA																		NA	NA				1517	4/29/2019	32.97347753	-75.91515687	-2587.381	343.12	-1.48	-3	0.8	
NA																		NA	NA				1518	4/29/2019	32.9734695	-75.91517019	-2587.576	348.55	0.29	-2.721	0.8	
NA																		NA	NA				1519	4/28/2019	32.97964373	-75.92866575	-2588.026	346.11	1.468	0.81	0.8	
NA																		NA	NA				1520	4/28/2019	32.97423089	-75.91799468	-2608.11	128.105	-4.844	0.015	1.5	
NA																		NA	NA				1521	4/28/2019	32.97423116	-75.9179943	-2608.07	128.17	-5.455	0.519	1.5	
NA																		NA	NA				1522	4/28/2019	32.97387259	-75.91788478	-2605.148	139.995	-10.825	1.435	3	
NA																		NA	NA				1523	4/28/2019	32.97959021	-75.92685999	-2592.994	271.479	-5.181	-1.467	1.1	
NA																		NA	NA				1524	4/28/2019	32.97959495	-75.92686218	-2592.98	271.42	-5.31	-1.518	1.1	
NA																		NA	NA				1525	4/28/2019	32.9795987	-75.92686414	-2593.012	271.447	-5.113	-1.537	1.1	
NA																		NA	NA				1526	4/28/2019	32.9796014	-75.92686596	-2592.977	271.439	-5.16	-0.769	1.1	
NA																		NA	NA				1527	4/28/2019	32.97958475	-75.92685756	-2592.994	271.621	-5.17	-1.687	1.1	
NA																		NA	NA				1528	4/28/2019	32.97960306	-75.92686774	-2592.997	271.69	-5.041	-0.266	1.1	
NA																		NA	NA				1529	4/28/2019	32.9796014	-75.92686596	-2592.977	271.439	-5.16	-0.769	1.1	
NA																		NA	NA				1530	4/28/2019	32.97960375	-75.9268693	-2592.963	271.78	-4.86	0.559	1.1	
NA																		NA	NA				1531	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
NA																		NA	NA				1532	4/28/2019	32.97967989	-75.92828061	-2590.762	6.72</				

RB1903 Master Sample Sheet

Sandra Brooke			Amanda Demopoulos				Andrea Quattrini		Nancy Prouty			Mandy Joye		Jason Chaytor		Mienis		Close													
Live.for.Growth Experiment	Live.1	Formalin.10.	LN2.3	RB1903.2019..	Formalin.10..1	ETOH.2	Frozen.at..20	RB1903.19..	X95.ETOH	X70..ETOH	Mud.Sample	Water.Sample	in.foll...20.C.	shells.rocks.skeleton	Mud.Sample.1	Water.Sample.1	Sediment.Chem	Fridge	Dried.Geology	Water.Sample.2	Skeleton.Sample	Water.Sample.3	id	date	lat_RENAV	long_RENAV	depth	heading	pitch	roll	altitude
NA								RB-19-217	x								NA	NA					1609	4/30/2019	31.90786669	-77.69564202	-770.921	65.404	-11.456	-0.091	4.2
NA	x							RB-19-218	x								NA	NA					1610	4/30/2019	31.90786669	-77.69564202	-770.921	65.404	-11.456	-0.091	4.2
NA								RB-19-219	x								NA	NA					1611	4/30/2019	31.90786669	-77.69564202	-770.921	65.404	-11.456	-0.091	4.2
NA																	NA	NA					1612	4/30/2019	31.90786669	-77.69564202	-770.921	65.404	-11.456	-0.091	4.2
NA								RB-19-220	x								NA	NA					1613	4/30/2019	31.90786669	-77.69564202	-770.921	65.404	-11.456	-0.091	4.2
NA																	NA	NA					1614	4/30/2019	31.90786669	-77.69564202	-770.921	65.404	-11.456	-0.091	4.2
NA																	NA	NA					1615	4/30/2019	31.90786669	-77.69564202	-770.921	65.404	-11.456	-0.091	4.2
NA																	NA	NA					1616	4/30/2019	31.90786669	-77.69564202	-770.921	65.404	-11.456	-0.091	4.2
NA																	NA	NA					1617	4/29/2019	31.89540213	-77.6981263	-660.698	347.08	-1.105	0.73	3.4
NA																	NA	NA					1618	4/29/2019	31.89540213	-77.6981263	-660.698	347.08	-1.105	0.73	3.4
NA																	NA	NA					1619	4/29/2019	31.89540213	-77.6981263	-660.698	347.08	-1.105	0.73	3.4
NA																	NA	NA					1620	4/29/2019	31.89540213	-77.6981263	-660.698	347.08	-1.105	0.73	3.4
NA																	NA	NA					1621	4/29/2019	31.89540213	-77.6981263	-660.698	347.08	-1.105	0.73	3.4
NA																	NA	NA					1622	4/29/2019	31.89540213	-77.6981263	-660.698	347.08	-1.105	0.73	3.4
NA																	NA	NA					1623	4/29/2019	31.89540213	-77.6981263	-660.698	347.08	-1.105	0.73	3.4
NA																	NA	NA					1624	4/29/2019	31.89540213	-77.6981263	-660.698	347.08	-1.105	0.73	3.4
NA																	NA	NA					1625	4/29/2019	31.89540213	-77.6981263	-660.698	347.08	-1.105	0.73	3.4
NA																	NA	NA					1626	4/29/2019	31.89540213	-77.6981263	-660.698	347.08	-1.105	0.73	3.4
NA																	NA	NA					1627	4/29/2019	31.89540213	-77.6981263	-660.698	347.08	-1.105	0.73	3.4
NA																	NA	NA					1628	4/29/2019	31.89540213	-77.6981263	-660.698	347.08	-1.105	0.73	3.4
NA																	NA	NA					1629	4/29/2019	31.89540213	-77.6981263	-660.698	347.08	-1.105	0.73	3.4
NA																	NA	NA					1630	4/29/2019	31.89540213	-77.6981263	-660.698	347.08	-1.105	0.73	3.4
NA																	NA	NA					1631	4/29/2019	31.89540213	-77.6981263	-660.698	347.08	-1.105	0.73	3.4
NA																	NA	NA					1632	4/29/2019	31.89540213	-77.6981263	-660.698	347.08	-1.105	0.73	3.4
NA																	NA	NA					1633	4/29/2019	31.89540213	-77.6981263	-660.698	347.08	-1.105	0.73	3.4
NA																	NA	NA					1634	4/29/2019	31.89540213	-77.6981263	-660.698	347.08	-1.105	0.73	3.4
NA																	NA	NA					1635	4/29/2019	31.89540213	-77.6981263	-660.698	347.08	-1.105	0.73	3.4
NA																	NA	NA					1636	4/29/2019	31.89540213	-77.6981263	-660.698	347.08	-1.105	0.73	3.4
NA																	NA	NA					1637	4/29/2019	31.89540213	-77.6981263	-660.698	347.08	-1.105	0.73	3.4
NA																	NA	NA					1638	4/29/2019	31.89540213	-77.6981263	-660.698	347.08	-1.105	0.73	3.4
NA																	NA	NA					1639	4/29/2019	31.89540213	-77.6981263	-660.698	347.08	-1.105	0.73	3.4
NA																	NA	NA					1640	4/30/2019	31.89815543	-77.69714341	-674.245	325.211	-8.929	4.048	3.3
NA																	NA	NA					1641	4/30/2019	31.89815543	-77.69714341	-674.245	325.211	-8.929	4.048	3.3
NA												x					NA	NA					1642	4/30/2019	31.89815543	-77.69714341	-674.245	325.211	-8.929	4.048	3.3
NA												x					NA	NA					1643	4/30/2019	31.89815543	-77.69714341	-674.245	325.211	-8.929	4.048	3.3

Appendix B - Plans of the Day (PODs)

RB1903 Plan of the Day

09 April 2019

depart Charleston

transit towards the Hoyt Hills site

31.66 -78.13

31 39.6 N 78 07.799 W

upon clearing the sea buoy, meeting on bridge to discuss Jason launch and recovery –

Chief Sci, Expedition leader, officers, bosun

1500 tour of Jason for science party

2200 (approximate time) When we reach ~500 m depth, evaluate the weather

if conditions are appropriate for USBL calibration, launch elevator

if seas/wind are too high, proceed to multibeam ops

survey plan will be provided by Brian Andrews

upon completion of either task, proceed to Richardson Hills

31.98443 -77.41139

31 59.065 N 77 24.683 W

10 April 2019

0700 CTD-02 @ Richardson Hills

0900 Launch elevator for USBL calibration

1800 recover elevator, evaluate weather conditions

if weather is conducive, Launch Jason dive J2-1128

or mapping around Richardson Hills

2000 arrive on station for ROV or MBES ops

RB-1903 Plan of the Day

11 April 2019

0800 recover ROV

proceed to lander deployment near ROV recovery location

lander seafloor target: 31d53.656 N, 77d21.599 W

survey over lander to determine precise location

1200 Launch J2-1129 @ Richardson Hills A4963 location

ROV seafloor target: 31d59.065 N, 77d24.683 W

1600 recover J2-1129

transit to next ROV deployment location

ROV seafloor target: 31d47.351 N, 77d29.870 W

2000 Launch J2-1130 @ Richardson Hills mounds site

12 April 2019

2000 Recover J2-1130

transit to lander location and recover lander

then CTD-03 near lander recovery site

RB-1903 Plan of the Day

11 April 2019

1800 Start multibeam mapping from Richardson to Blake Deep

12 April 2019

Waiting On Weather (WOW) – if coming down, proceed to ROV ops

 If weather improves near Blake Deep, proceed to that dive plan
 otherwise continue mapping

TBD Launch J2-1129 @ Richardson Hills A4963 location

 ROV seafloor target: 31d59.065 N, 77d24.683 W

 4 hr dive (might do this short dive on the 13th if WOW is long)

transit to next ROV deployment location

 ROV seafloor target: 31d47.351 N, 77d29.870 W

Launch J2-1130 @ Richardson Hills mounds site

 dive time will depend on length of WOW

after recovery of J2-1130, transit to lander location

13 April 2019

CTD-05 near lander recovery site

Recover lander at first light

0800 Launch J2-1131 at Blake Deep

14 April 2019

J2-1132 at Stetson Banks

RB-1903 Plan of the Day

12 April 2019

on arrival CTD-05 @ Stetson Banks bowl site

followed by Launch J2-1129 @ Stetson Banks bowl site

32d07.415 N, 77d39.449 W, 670 m depth

13 April 2019

0800 recover J2-1129

transit to lander location

triangulated position: 31d53.97 N, 77d21.222 W

1000 recover lander

transit to transit to Blake Deep, CTD-06 on arrival

1200 Launch J2-1130 at Blake Deep

31d17.58 N, 85d26.35, 1400 m

14 April 2019

0400 recover J2-1130

0800 launch J2-1131 @ Richardson A4963

ROV seafloor target: 31d59.065 N, 77d24.683 W, 750 m

1200 recover J2-1131

1400 re-deploy lander at previous location

drop it (approximately) here: 31d53.82 N, 77d21.32 W

triangulate lander

transit to Blake (Popenoe) Mounds

15 April 2019

CTD-07 on arrival

0800 J2-1132 at Popenoe (Blake) Mounds

31d03.690 N, 79d30.726 W, 700 m

2000 recover J2-1132

transit to Charleston

16 April 2019

0730 arrive at sea buoy

RB-1903 Plan of the Day

13 April 2019

1200 CTD-05 @ Richardson A4963

when the seas come down: launch J2-1129 @ Richardson A4963

ROV seafloor target: 31d59.065 N, 77d24.683 W, 750 m

14 April 2019

1200 recover J2-1129

1400 re-deploy lander at previous location

drop it (approximately) here: 31d53.82 N, 77d21.32 W

triangulate lander

transit to Blake Mounds

15 April 2019

CTD-06 on arrival

0800 J2-1130 at Blake Mounds

31d03.690 N, 79d30.726 W, 700 m

2000 recover J2-1130

transit to Charleston

16 April 2019

0730 arrive at sea buoy

RB-1903
Plan of the Day

14 April 2019

transit to Hoyt Hills to conduct brief MBES patch test and survey
continue transit to Blake Mounds

15 April 2019

CTD-07 on arrival

0800 J2-1130 at Blake Mounds

two potential starting points

if we get in at 0800: 31d03.001 N, 79d30.764 W, 685 m

if we get in at 1200: 31d03.788 N, 79d31.678 W, 567 m

2000 transit to Charleston

16 April 2019

0730 arrive at sea buoy

RB1903 Plan of the Day

16 April 2019

1000 depart Charleston

transit towards the Savannah Banks site

31.7679 N -79.20477W

31 46.075 N -79 12.29699 W

tour of Jason for new science party, drills, etc.

1600 (approximate time) on station- CTD cast

1800 Launch ROV (J2-1130)

17 April 2019

0800 Recover ROV

0900 Head to Blake Deep (9 hrs transit)

31.293 -77.243

31 18.2960 N -77 14.375 W

1800 CTD on arrival

2000 ROV dive (J2-1131)

18 April 2019

0800 recover ROV, transit to Blake Ridge

32.494 -76.199

32 29.638 N -76 11.821W

1600 CTD on arrival

1800 ROV Dive (J2-1132) (weather depending)

19 April 2019

0600 Recover ROV, transit to Lookout Deep

33.923 -75.812

33 55.386 -75 48.716W

1500 CTD or XBT upon arrival, then multibeam map

1800 ROV dive TBD

RB1903
Plan of the Day

17 April 2019

~0900 Recover ROV

1000 Head to Blake Deep (9 hrs transit)

31.293 -77.243

31 18.2960 N -77 14.375 W

On arrival ROV dive (J2-1131)

18 April 2019

1200 recover ROV

1300 CTD

Multibeam to cover some holidays at the north end of feature (tracklines will be given to the bridge, target area: 31 23.641N -77 13.408W) and then transit to safe harbor

19 April 2019

Waiting on Weather

20 April 2019

Head to Lookout Deep:

33.923N, -75.812W

33 55.386 -75 48.716W

Activities: CTD or XBT upon arrival, then multibeam map to

refine dive target

ROV dive (12-18 hrs)

RB1903
Plan of the Day

20 April 2019

Head to Lookout Deep:

Starting line – point #1:

34.02686N, -75.77626 W

34 01.612 -75 46.576W

Activities: Map Map MAP

21 April 2019

Head to Pamlico Canyon when mapping is complete

Triangulate the lander if conditions allow

Lander location:

34.92354N, -75.15117W

34 55.413N, -75 09.070W

1936m

CTD* cast until ROV ops can be initiated

CTD #	Long DD	Lat DD	Long DM	Lat DM	Station	Depth (m)
1	-75.2245	34.97216	-75 13.470	34 58.330	Pamlico	694
2	-75.2006	34.95279	-75 12.036	34 57.167	Pamlico	1113
3	-75.1705	34.93638	-75 10.230	34 56.183	Pamlico	1394
4	-75.1519	34.92395	-75 09.114	34 55.437	Pamlico	1930
5	-75.1248	34.90709	-75 07.488	34 54.435	Pamlico	2524

*Note, these casts can be done in any order, and starting CTD can be closest to lander location.

ROV dive (24 hrs)

Target onbottom:

34.92796N, -75.1495W

34 55.6776N, -75 08.9700W

Depth: 1820 m

22 April 2019

Recover ROV

Transit to Pea Island

CTD cast

ROV dive (24hrs):

35.675N, -74.794W

35 40.473N, -74 47.647W

Depth: 318m

23 April 2019

Recover ROV

Transit to Kitty Hawk

CTD cast

ROV dive

RB1903
Plan of the Day

22 April 2019

1200 Recover ROV

CTD cast at:

34.93488, -75.165817

34 56.092033N, -75 9.950883W

1607m

Transit to Pea Island (4.5hrs)

CTD cast with monoco

35.673N, -74.795W

35 40.410N, -74 47.71W

~2000: ROV dive (12 hrs):

35.675N, -74.794W

35 40.473N, -74 47.647W

Depth: 318m

23 April 2019

0800 Recover ROV

CTD cast at recovery location

Transit to Kitty Hawk (<2 hrs)

CTD cast upon arrival after USBL pole deployment

Approximate location:

35 55.5639N, -74 48.635W

ROV dive (12 hrs)

RB1903

Plan of the Day

23 April 2019

~0000: ROV dive-J2-1133 (12 hrs):

35.675N, -74.794W

35 40.473N, -74 47.647W

Depth: 318m

1200 Recover ROV

2 CTD casts

CTD #12: background spot, D=353 m

35.6767N, -74.79552W

35 40.600N, -74 47.721W

CTD #13: Mat, bubble spot:

35.67556, -74.79550W, 312m

35 40.5336, -74 47.7306

Transit to Kitty Hawk

24 April 2019

0000 Dive at Kitty Hawk (12 hrs, J2-1134)

Tentative target:

35.92773N, -74.80815W

35 55.66378N, -74 48.4896W

D=398m

1200 recover Kitty Hawk, set up for 2 CTD casts

CTD #14 target: wherever Jason is recovered

CTD # 15:

35.93414N, -74.8182W, D= 233

35 56.04861N, -74 49.0929W

Transit to Keller Canyon (2hrs)

Tentative location:

35.5447N, -74.7829W

35 32.68217N, -74 46.974W

D=1151m

25 April 2019

Keller Canyon

00:00-12:00-Dive: J2-1135, 12 hrs

CTD at ROV recover location/within the canyon (if feasible)

Transit to Hatteras Canyon (2hrs)

35.2854N, -74.9054W

35 17.1236N, -74 54.325W

D=957m

26 April 2019

Hatteras Canyon

Dive: J2-1136

00:00-12:00, 12 hrs

CTD at ROV recovery location/within the canyon (if feasible)

TBD based on review of new mapping data:

Transit to Cape Lookout (9) or Cape Fear (15hrs)

RB1903
Plan of the Day

25 April 2019

Transit to Cape Fear Seep (~6 hrs)

32.97N, -75.932W

32 58.42N, -75 55.95W

D= 2600m

Multibeam with water column en route and over site

26 April 2019

Transit mapping/Map SW of Blake Ridge Seep

Multibeam en route with water column

CTD upon arrival at Blake Ridge Seep

27 April 2019

Transit to Blake Ridge seep (depending on weather report, break off from mapping to arrive 0400/0600)

Blake Ridge Seep (4hrs)

32.494N, -76.199W

32 29657N, -76 11.928W

1200-2359– Dive at Blake Ridge Seep (12hrs) (or earlier if conditions look dive-able)

CTD either before or after dive, depending on conditions

28 April 2019

Transit to Cape Fear Seep (~3 hrs)

32.97N, -75.932W

32 58.42N, -75 55.95W

D= 2600m

0400-1800 Dive at Cape Fear Seep (16hrs)

CTD at the dive site

Transit to Blake Mounds (31 21.44N, -79 01.026W, 17 hrs)

1600: Dive on Blake Mounds (24 hrs)

29 April 2019:

0800: recover, CTD

Steam to Charleston

Appendix C - Dive Plans

RB-1903 – DEEP SEARCH

Dive: J2-1128

Launch: 2000 on 04/10/19

Site: Richardson Hills

Seafloor Target: 31d52.813 N, 77d22.433 W

Basket: 16 push cores on swing arms, 6 sample quivers on swing arms, 4 niskins, 5-chamber slurp, 2 large bioboxes, 3 coral pots, additional sample quivers

Note: make sure lasers are on for all transits, off for glamor shots

1. Get settled on the bottom, begin transit towards WPT1
2. take one set of 4 push cores at the start if you find a suitable place
3. Start up the slope to WPT2, continue through all WPTs
 - a. Make note of substrate type, current direction, fauna
4. At any point that you find a decent amount of Lophelia, mussel pot
 - a. Only turn T-handle counter-clockwise when handling
 - b. Push into coral, turning counter-clockwise
 - c. When it's in, engage ram on manipulator
 - d. Turn mussel pot clockwise
 - e. Keep turning until you see the black mark on string
 - f. Pick it up and return to holster
5. When you see them, collect a diversity of corals
 - a. Octocorals and antipatharians into quivers
 - i. Plumarella or something else with good numbers
 - b. Scleractinians into biobox (Enallopsamia and Lophelia)
6. Continue across the swales
 - a. Another set of push cores
 - b. More coral collections
 - c. Another mussel pot
7. Near the end, trip the niskins around a lot of live Lophelia
8. Come home

RB-1903 – DEEP SEARCH

Dive: J2-1129

Launch: 1500 on 04/13/19 Site: Richardson A4963

Seafloor Target: 31d59.07 N, 77d24.75 W, 800 m depth

Basket: 11 push cores on port swing arm, 8 sample quivers on stbd swing arm, 4 niskins, 5-chamber slurp, 2 large bioboxes (1 with inserts, 1 without), 3 markers, 3 coral pots, milk crate, McLean Pump

Notes: Make sure lasers are on for all transits, off for glamor shots

When transitioning from sitting to transiting, white balance (one push)

Watch leads should take copious notes in notebook

Quivers 3 and 4 are set up for microbial samples – only 1 species in each

1. Once you are in good coral territory, deploy McLean pump – get a good fix
2. Take a set of push cores if you can and a rock if you see one
3. Begin transit towards Transplant site
 - a. Search for transplants and recover them into biobox
4. Take a coral pot
 - a. Only turn T-handle counter-clockwise when handling
 - b. Push into coral, turning counter-clockwise
 - c. When it's in, engage ram on manipulator
 - d. Turn mussel pot clockwise
 - e. Keep turning until you see the black mark on string
 - f. Pick it up and return to holster
5. When you see them, collect a diversity of corals
 - a. Octocorals and antipatharians into quivers
 - i. Plumarella or white plexaurid with good numbers
 - b. Scleractinians into biobox (Enallopsamia and Lophelia)
6. When further away from 1st one, take another mussel pot, and then another
7. Start N towards WPT 2 and 3
 - a. Last mussel pot, more octocoral collections, more push cores
8. Return to McLean deployment location
9. trip the niskins then recover McLean pump

RB-1903 – DEEP SEARCH

Dive: J2-1130

Launch: 1800 on 04/16/19 Site: Savannah Banks

Seafloor Target: 31 46.075 N -79 12.295 W, 535 m depth

Corals	Ideal collection needs	location
Lophelia	1 big collection, 10 small	biobox, 3 mussel pots
Enallopsammia	>10	quivers
Desmophyllum	>10	quivers or biobox
Madrepora	?	quivers or biobox
Plumarella	10	quivers
white plexaurid	10	quivers
other octocorals	opportunistic	quivers
other cup corals	opportunistic	quivers

Other critter needs	Ideal collection needs	location
Eumunida	opportunistic	slurp
Other squat lobsters	opportunistic	slurp
Asteroschema	opportunistic	biobox/quivers/slurp
Echinus	opportunistic	biobox
Sponges	opportunistic	

Basket: 11 push cores on port swing arm, 8 sample quivers on stbd swing arm, 4 niskins, 5-chamber slurp, 2 large bioboxes (6 inserts), 3 markers, 3 coral pots, milk crate for ROCKS

Notes: Make sure lasers are on for all transits, off for glamor shots

When transitioning from sitting to transiting, white balance (one push)

Watch leads should take copious notes in notebook

All quivers except #7 are set up for microbial samples – only 1 species in each (3 minimum, 5 ideal Enallopsammia or Desmophyllum)

1. Take a set of push cores if you can and a rock if you see one
2. Transit to WP1, find a good coral collection site
3. When you see them, collect a diversity of corals (**SEE TABLE**)
 - a. Octocorals, antipatharians, Enallopsammia into quivers
 - b. Scleractinians into biobox (Lophelia, Desmophyllum, Madrepora)
4. Take a coral pot
 - a. Only turn T-handle counter-clockwise when handling
 - b. Push into coral, turning counter-clockwise
 - c. When it's in, engage ram on manipulator

- d. Turn pot clockwise
 - e. Keep turning until you see the black mark on string
 - f. Pick it up and return to holster
5. Head towards WPT 2
 - a. Collect corals, 2nd coral pot, more push cores, rocks
 6. Head towards WPT 3
 - a. Collect corals, last coral pot, more push cores, rocks
 7. trip the niskins then continue until all the basket is loaded

RB-1903 – DEEP SEARCH

Dive: J2-1131

Launch: 1800 on 04/17/19 Site: Blake Deep

Seafloor Target: 31 17.151 N -77 14.229 W, 1365 m depth

Corals	Ideal collection needs	location
Solenosmilia	10	quivers/biobox
Desmophyllum	>10	quivers or biobox
Enallopsammia	>10	quivers
Madrepora	some	quivers or biobox
Plumarella	10	quivers
Bamboo corals	10	quivers/biobox
Plexaurids	10	quivers
Antipatharians	opportunistic	quivers/biobox
other octocorals	opportunistic	quivers
other cup corals	opportunistic	quivers

Other critter needs	Ideal collection needs	location
Eumunida	opportunistic	slurp
Other squat lobsters	opportunistic	slurp
Asteroschema	opportunistic	biobox/quivers/slurp
Echinus	opportunistic	biobox
Sponges	opportunistic	biobox/quivers
Acesta (bivalve)	opportunistic	biobox

Basket: 11 push cores on port swing arm, 8 sample quivers on stbd swing arm, 4 niskins, 5-chamber slurp, 2 large bioboxes (6 inserts), 3 coral pots, milk crate for ROCKS, 3 markers, 3 small stoppers, SCOOP

Notes: Make sure lasers are on for all transits, off for glamor shots

When transitioning from sitting to transiting, white balance (one push)

Watch leads should take copious notes in notebook

All quivers except #7 are set up for microbial samples – only 1 species in each (3 minimum, 5 ideal Desmophyllum)

1. Take a set of push cores if you can and a rock if you see one
2. Transit to WP1, find a good coral collection site
3. When you see them, collect a diversity of corals (**SEE TABLE**)
 - a. Octocorals, antipatharians, Desmophyllum into quivers
 - b. Scleractinians into biobox (Solenosmilia, Madrepora)
4. Take a coral pot
 - a. Only turn T-handle counter-clockwise when handling

- b. Push into coral, turning counter-clockwise
 - c. When it's in, engage ram on manipulator
 - d. Turn pot clockwise
 - e. Keep turning until you see the black mark on string
 - f. Pick it up and return to holster
5. Head towards WPT 2
 - a. Collect corals, 2nd coral pot, more push cores, rocks
 6. Head towards WPT 3
 - a. Collect corals, last coral pot, more push cores, rocks
 7. Head towards WPT 4
 - a. Collect corals, last coral pot, more push cores, rocks
 8. Head towards WPT 5
 - a. Collect corals, last coral pot, more push cores, rocks
 9. trip the niskins then continue until all the basket is loaded
 10. If you reach the top of the feature, just run across the platform until the end of dive

RB-1903 – DEEP SEARCH

Dive: J2-1132 Launch: 1200 on 04/21/19 Site: Pamlico Canyon
Seafloor Target: 34 55.533 N -75 08.955 W, 1820 m depth

Corals	Ideal collection needs	location
Desmophyllum	>10	quivers or biobox
Paramuricea	>10	quivers or biobox
Solenosmilia	10	quivers/biobox
Dominant octocorals (e.g.):		
Acanthogorgia		
Paragorgia		
Bamboo corals		quivers/biobox
Plexaurids		quivers
Antipatharians	opportunistic	quivers/biobox
other octocorals	opportunistic	quivers
other cup corals	opportunistic	quivers

Other critters	Ideal collection needs	location
Asteroschema	opportunistic	biobox/quivers/slurp
Eumunida	opportunistic	slurp
Other squat lobsters	opportunistic	slurp
Echinus	opportunistic	biobox
Sponges	opportunistic	biobox/quivers
Acesta (bivalve-1 2)	opportunistic	biobox

Basket: 16 push cores on skid, 11 push cores on port swing arm, 8 sample quivers on stbd swing arm, 5 quivers on skid, 4 niskins, 5-chamber slurp with small mesh, 1 large biobox (4 inserts), 2 coral pots, 1 milk crate and 1 MP holder for ROCKS and coral bases, 5 markers, 5 small stoppers, SCOOP

Imagery:

Make sure lasers are on for all transits, off for glamor shots
 White balance (one push) when sitting down or starting transiting
 Set up shot, then hands off controller for 10-20 secs

Notes: Watch leads should take copious notes in notebook, **if you see trash, pick it up if it doesn't impact science or is dangerous.**

All quivers ON STARBOARD SWINGARM except #7 are set up for microbial samples – only 1 species in each (3 minimum, 5 ideal Desmophyllum or Paramuricea)

1. Take a set of 7 push cores if you can and a rock if you see one
2. Transit to WP1, find a good coral collection site
3. When you see them, collect a diversity of corals (**SEE TABLE**)
 - a. Octocorals, antipatharians, *Desmophyllum* into quivers
 - b. Scleractinians into biobox (*Solenosmilia*)
4. Take a coral pot (if possible-**Solenosmilia**)
 - a. Only turn T-handle counter-clockwise when handling
 - b. Push into coral, turning counter-clockwise
 - c. When it's in, engage ram on manipulator
 - d. Turn pot clockwise
 - e. Keep turning until you see the black mark on string
 - f. Pick it up and return to holster
5. Head towards WPT 2
 - a. Collect corals, 2nd coral pot, 6 push cores, rocks
6. Head towards WPT 3
 - a. Collect corals, last coral pot, 6 push cores, rocks
7. Head towards WPT 4
 - a. Collect corals, 6 push cores, rocks
8. Head towards WPT 5
 - a. Collect corals, last coral pot, more push cores, rocks
9. trip the niskins **near lots of coral** then continue until all the basket is loaded
10. If you reach the top of the feature, just run across the platform until the end of dive

RB-1903 – DEEP SEARCH

Dive: J2-1133

Launch: 0000 Site: Pea Island Seep

Seafloor Target: 35.675 N, -74.794W, 35 40.473N, -74 47.647W

Depth: 318 m

m depth

Corals	Ideal collection needs	location
Dominant octocorals (e.g.):		
Bamboo corals		quivers/biobox
Antipatharians	opportunistic	quivers/biobox
cup corals		
Other critters	Ideal collection needs	location
Mussels/Clams		
Asteroschema	opportunistic	biobox/quivers/slurp
Eumunida	opportunistic	slurp
Other squat lobsters	opportunistic	slurp
Echinus	opportunistic	biobox
Sponges	opportunistic	biobox/quivers
Other seep associates	opportunistic	biobox/quivers

Basket: 21 push cores on skid, 11 push cores on port swing arm, 8 sample quivers on stbd swing arm (7 ultracleaned), 4 niskins, 5-chamber slurp with small mesh, 1 large biobox (4 inserts), 2 mussel pots, 1 milk crate and 1 MP holder for ROCKS and coral bases, 5 markers, 5 small stoppers, SCOOP

Imagery:

Make sure lasers are on for all transits, off for glamor shots

White balance (one push) when sitting down or starting transiting

Set up shot, then hands off controller for 10-20 secs

Notes: Watch leads should take copious notes in notebook, **if you see trash, pick it up if it doesn't impact science or is dangerous.**

All quivers ON STARBOARD SWINGARM except #7 are set up for microbial samples – only 1 species in each (3 minimum, 5 ideal Desmophyllum, Acanthogorgia, or Paramuricea)

1. Find seep (mat, hydrate, carbonate)
2. Take a set of 8 push cores if you can and a rock if you see one
3. Transit to WP1, find a good collection site

4. When you see them, collect a diversity of organisms (**SEE TABLE**)
5. **Slurp mat** (use same chamber at multiple sites)
6. Take a mussel pot (if possible -**Bathymodiolus or clams**)
 - a. Only turn T-handle counter-clockwise when handling
 - b. Push into coral, turning counter-clockwise
 - c. When it's in, engage ram on manipulator
 - d. Turn pot clockwise
 - e. Keep turning until you see the black mark on string
 - f. Pick it up and return to holster
7. Head towards WPT 2
 - a. Collect animals, 2nd mussel pot, 8 push cores, rocks
8. Head towards WPT 3
 - a. Collect animals, 3rd mussel pot, 8 push cores, rocks
9. Head towards WPT 4
 - a. Collect animals, 8 push cores, rocks
10. Head towards WPT 5
 - a. Collect animals, more push cores, rocks
11. trip 3 Niskins **CLOSE TO THE END OF THE DIVE** (near mussels, mats, bubbles, something seepy) then continue until all the basket is loaded
12. If you reach the top of the feature, just run across the platform until the end of dive

Push core plan:

8 in non seep
8 in bubble
2 sets of 8 in mats

Niskin plan:

1 niskin (#1 or 2) in bubbles
3 Niskins in seepy habitat

Rock plan:

Larger the better, variety of sites (Nancy/Jason to guide)
5 rocks, 4 in biobox inserts, 1 in rockbox/mussel pot holder

RB-1903 – DEEP SEARCH

Dive: J2-1134 Launch: 2000 on 04/23/19 Site: Kitty Hawk Seep
Seafloor Target: 35.92515N, -74.8053W, 35 55.509N, -74 48.3156W
Depth: 471m

	Ideal collection	
Corals	needs	location
Lophelia		
Dominant octocorals (e.g.):		
Bamboo corals		quivers/biobox
Antipatharians	opportunistic	quivers/biobox
cup corals		
	Ideal collection	
Other critters	needs	location
Mussels/Clams		
Tube worms		
Quill worms		
Asteroschema	opportunistic	biobox/quivers/slurp
Eumunida	opportunistic	slurp
Other squat lobsters	opportunistic	slurp
Echinus	opportunistic	biobox
Sponges	opportunistic	biobox/quivers
Other seep associates	opportunistic	biobox/quivers

Basket: 21 push cores on skid, 11 push cores on port swing arm, 8 sample quivers on stbd swing arm (7 ultracleaned), 4 niskins, 5-chamber slurp with small mesh, 1 large biobox (4 inserts), 2 mussel pots, 1 milk crate and 1 MP holder for ROCKS and coral bases, 5 markers, 5 small stoppers, SCOOP

Imagery:

Make sure lasers are on for all transits, off for glamor shots
 White balance (one push) when sitting down or starting transiting
 Set up shot, then hands off controller for 10-20 secs

Notes: Watch leads should take copious notes in notebook, **if you see trash, pick it up if it doesn't impact science or is dangerous.**

All quivers ON STARBOARD SWINGARM except #7 are set up for microbial samples – only 1 species in each (3 minimum, 5 ideal Desmophyllum, Acanthogorgia, or Paramuricea)

1. Find seep (mat, hydrate, carbonate)
2. Take a set of 8 push cores if you can and a rock if you see one

3. Transit to WP1, find a good collection site
4. When you see them, collect a diversity of organisms (**SEE TABLE**)
5. Slurp mat (can use same chamber at multiple sites)
6. Take a mussel pot (if possible-**Bathymodiolus or clams**)
 - a. Only turn T-handle counter-clockwise when handling
 - b. Push into coral, turning counter-clockwise
 - c. When it's in, engage ram on manipulator
 - d. Turn pot clockwise
 - e. Keep turning until you see the black mark on string
 - f. Pick it up and return to holster
7. Head towards WPT 2
 - a. Collect animals, 2nd mussel pot, 8 push cores, rocks
8. Head towards WPT 3
 - a. Collect animals, 8 push cores, rocks
9. Head towards WPT 4
 - a. Collect animals, 8 push cores, rocks
10. Head towards WPT 5
 - a. Collect animals, more push cores, rocks
11. Head towards WPT 5
 - a. Collect animals, more push cores, rocks
12. trip 3 Niskins **CLOSE TO THE END OF THE DIVE** (near mussels, mats, bubbles, something seepy) then continue until all the basket is loaded
13. If you reach the top of the feature, just run across the platform until the end of dive

Push core plan:

8 in non seep
8 in bubble
2 sets of 8 in mats

Niskin plan:

1 niskin (#1 or 2) in bubbles
3 Niskins in seepy habitat

Rock plan:

Larger the better, variety of sites (Nancy/Jason to guide)
5 rocks, 4 in biobox inserts, 1 in rockbox/mussel pot holder

RB-1903 – DEEP SEARCH

Dive: J2-1135 Launch: 0000 on 04/25/19 Site: Cape Lookout DEEP
Seafloor Target: 33 54.9594N -75 49.9632W, 1015 m depth

	Ideal collection	
Corals	needs	location
Desmophyllum	>10	quivers or biobox
Paramuricea	>10	quivers or biobox
Solenosmilia	10	quivers/biobox
Dominant octocorals (e.g.):		
Acanthogorgia		
Paragorgia		
Bamboo corals		quivers/biobox
Plexaurids		quivers
Antipatharians	opportunistic	quivers/biobox
other octocorals	opportunistic	quivers
other cup corals	opportunistic	quivers

	Ideal collection	
Other critters	needs	location
Asteroschema	opportunistic	biobox/quivers/slurp
Eumunida	opportunistic	slurp
Other squat lobsters	opportunistic	slurp
Echinus	opportunistic	biobox
Sponges	opportunistic	biobox/quivers
Acesta (bivalve-1 2)	opportunistic	biobox

Basket: 16 push cores on skid, 11 push cores on port swing arm, 8 sample quivers on stbd swing arm, 5 coral quivers on skid, 4 niskins, 5-chamber slurp with small mesh, 1 large biobox (4 inserts), 2 coral pots, 1 milk crate and 1 MP holder for ROCKS and coral bases (e.g., Desmophyllum, Bamboo), 5 markers, 5 small stoppers, SCOOP

Imagery:

Make sure lasers are on for all transits, off for glamor shots
 White balance (one push) when sitting down or starting transiting
 Set up shot, then hands off controller for 10-20 secs

Notes: Watch leads should take copious notes in notebook, **if you see trash, pick it up if it doesn't impact science or is dangerous.**

All quivers ON STARBOARD SWINGARM except #7 are set up for microbial samples – only 1 species in each (3 minimum, 5 ideal **Desmophyllum or **Acanthogorgia**)**

1. Take a set of 7 push cores if you can and a rock if you see one
2. Transit to WP1, find a good coral collection site
3. When you see them, collect a diversity of corals (**SEE TABLE**)
 - a. Octocorals, antipatharians, Desmophyllum into quivers
 - b. Scleractinians into biobox (Solenosmilia)
4. Take a coral pot (if possible-**Solenosmilia**)
 - a. Only turn T-handle counter-clockwise when handling
 - b. Push into coral, turning counter-clockwise
 - c. When it's in, engage ram on manipulator
 - d. Turn pot clockwise
 - e. Keep turning until you see the black mark on string
 - f. Pick it up and return to holster
5. Head towards WPT 2
 - a. Collect corals, 2nd coral pot, 6 push cores, rocks
6. Head towards WPT 3
 - a. Collect corals, last coral pot, 6 push cores, rocks
7. Head towards WPT 4
 - a. Collect corals, 6 push cores, rocks
8. Head towards WPT 5
 - a. Collect corals, last coral pot, more push cores, rocks
9. trip the niskins **near lots of coral** then continue until all the basket is loaded
10. If you reach the top of the feature, just run across the platform until the end of dive

RB-1903 – DEEP SEARCH

Dive: J2-1135 Launch: 0000 on 04/25/19 Site: Keller Canyon
Seafloor Target: 35.5447 N -74.7829W, 1000 m depth

	Ideal collection needs	location
Corals		
Desmophyllum	>10	quivers or biobox
Paramuricea	>10	quivers or biobox
Solenosmilia	10	quivers/biobox
Dominant octocorals (e.g.):		
Acanthogorgia		
Paragorgia		
Bamboo corals		quivers/biobox
Plexaurids		quivers
Antipatharians	opportunistic	quivers/biobox
other octocorals	opportunistic	quivers
other cup corals	opportunistic	quivers

	Ideal collection needs	location
Other critters		
Asteroschema	opportunistic	biobox/quivers/slurp
Eumunida	opportunistic	slurp
Other squat lobsters	opportunistic	slurp
Echinus	opportunistic	biobox
Sponges	opportunistic	biobox/quivers
Acesta (bivalve-1 2)	opportunistic	biobox

Basket: 16 push cores on skid, 11 push cores on port swing arm, 8 sample quivers on stbd swing arm, 5 coral quivers on skid, 4 niskins, 5-chamber slurp with small mesh, 1 large biobox (4 inserts), 2 coral pots, 1 milk crate and 1 MP holder for ROCKS and coral bases (e.g., Desmophyllum, Bamboo), 5 markers, 5 small stoppers, SCOOP

Imagery:

Make sure lasers are on for all transits, off for glamor shots
 White balance (one push) when sitting down or starting transiting
 Set up shot, then hands off controller for 10-20 secs

Notes: Watch leads should take copious notes in notebook, **if you see trash, pick it up if it doesn't impact science or is dangerous.**

All quivers ON STARBOARD SWINGARM except #7 are set up for microbial samples – only 1 species in each (3 minimum, 5 ideal **Desmophyllum or **Acanthogorgia**)**

1. Take a set of 7 push cores if you can and a rock if you see one
2. Transit to WP1, find a good coral collection site
3. When you see them, collect a diversity of corals (**SEE TABLE**)
 - a. Octocorals, antipatharians, Desmophyllum into quivers
 - b. Scleractinians into biobox (Solenosmilia)
4. Take a coral pot (if possible-**Solenosmilia**)
 - a. Only turn T-handle counter-clockwise when handling
 - b. Push into coral, turning counter-clockwise
 - c. When it's in, engage ram on manipulator
 - d. Turn pot clockwise
 - e. Keep turning until you see the black mark on string
 - f. Pick it up and return to holster
5. Head towards WPT 2
 - a. Collect corals, 2nd coral pot, 6 push cores, rocks
6. Head towards WPT 3
 - a. Collect corals, last coral pot, 6 push cores, rocks
7. Head towards WPT 4
 - a. Collect corals, 6 push cores, rocks
8. Head towards WPT 5
 - a. Collect corals, last coral pot, more push cores, rocks
9. trip the niskins **near lots of coral** then continue until all the basket is loaded
10. If you reach the top of the feature, just run across the platform until the end of dive

RB-1903 – DEEP SEARCH

Dive: J2-1136 Launch: xxxx on 04/27/19 Site: Blake Ridge Seep
Seafloor Target: 32.3937N, -76.19115W, 32 29.6248N, -76 11.4692W
Depth: 2193 m

Corals	Ideal collection needs	location
Dominant octocorals (e.g.):		
Bamboo corals		quivers/biobox
Antipatharians	opportunistic	quivers/biobox
cup corals		
Other critters	Ideal collection needs	location
Mussels/Clams	target mix of sizes	biobox/quivers/slurp (small)
Asteroschema	opportunistic	biobox/quivers/slurp
Eumunida	opportunistic	slurp
Other squat lobsters	opportunistic	slurp
Echinus	opportunistic	biobox
Sponges	opportunistic	biobox/quivers
Other seep associates	opportunistic	biobox/quivers

Basket: 21 push cores on skid, 11 push cores on port swing arm, 8 sample quivers on stbd swing arm (7 ultracleaned), 4 niskins, 5-chamber slurp with small mesh, 1 large biobox (4 inserts), 3 mussel pots, 1 milk crate for ROCKS and coral bases, 5 small stoppers, 1 marker, SCOOP

Imagery:

Make sure lasers are on for all transits, off for glamor shots
 White balance (one push) when sitting down or starting transiting
 Set up shot, then hands off controller for 10-20 secs

Notes: Watch leads should take copious notes in notebook, **if you see trash, pick it up if it doesn't impact science or is dangerous.**

All quivers ON STARBOARD SWINGARM except #7 are set up for microbial samples – only 1 species in each (3 minimum, 5 ideal Desmophyllum, Acanthogorgia, or Paramuricea)

1. Find seep (mat, hydrate, carbonate)
2. Take a set of 8 push cores if you can and a rock if you see one
3. Transit to WP1, find a good collection site
4. When you see them, collect a diversity of organisms (SEE TABLE)

5. **Slurp mat** (use same chamber at multiple sites)
6. Take a mussel pot (**Bathymodiolus**)
 - a. Only turn T-handle counter-clockwise when handling
 - b. Push into coral, turning counter-clockwise
 - c. When it's in, engage ram on manipulator
 - d. Turn pot clockwise
 - e. Keep turning until you see the black mark on string
 - f. Pick it up and return to holster
7. Head towards WPT 2
 - a. Collect animals, 2nd mussel pot, 8 push cores, rocks
8. Head towards WPT 3
 - a. Collect animals, 3rd mussel pot, 8 push cores, rocks
9. Head towards WPT 4
 - a. Collect animals, 8 push cores, rocks
10. Head towards WPT 5
 - a. Collect animals, more push cores, rocks
11. trip 3 Niskins **CLOSE TO THE END OF THE DIVE** (near mussels, mats, bubbles, something seepy) then continue until all the basket is loaded
12. If you reach the top of the feature, just run across the platform until the end of dive

Mussel Collections:

3 different patch sizes (small, medium, large, 3-5 each patch)

Target different mussel sizes – no need to actually measure them on the seafloor
dead shells

Push core plan:

8 by mussels

8 by clams

2 sets of 8 in mats

Niskin plan:

1 niskin (#1 or 2) in bubbles

3 Niskins in seepy habitat

Rock plan:

variety of sites (Nancy/Jason to guide), 2-3

RB-1903 – DEEP SEARCH

Dive: J2-1137 Launch: 1200 on 04/28/19 Site: Cape Fear Seep
Seafloor Target: 32.97918N, -75.92864W, 32 58.7508, -75 55.7184W
Depth: 2676 m

Corals	Ideal collection needs	location
Dominant octocorals (e.g.):		
Bamboo corals		quivers/biobox
Antipatharians	opportunistic	quivers/biobox
cup corals		
Other critters	Ideal collection needs	location
Mussels/Clams	target mix of sizes	biobox/quivers/slurp (small)
Asteroschema	opportunistic	biobox/quivers/slurp
Eumunida	opportunistic	slurp
Other squat lobsters	opportunistic	slurp
Echinus	opportunistic	biobox
Sponges	opportunistic	biobox/quivers
Other seep associates	opportunistic	biobox/quivers

Basket: 21 push cores on skid, 11 push cores on port swing arm, 8 sample quivers on stbd swing arm (7 ultracleaned), 4 niskins, 5-chamber slurp with small mesh, 1 large biobox (4 inserts), 3 mussel pots, 1 milk crate for ROCKS and coral bases, 5 small stoppers, 1 marker, SCOOP

Imagery:

Make sure lasers are on for all transits, off for glamor shots
 White balance (one push) when sitting down or starting transiting
 Set up shot, then hands off controller for 10-20 secs

Notes: Watch leads should take copious notes in notebook, **if you see trash, pick it up if it doesn't impact science or is dangerous.**

1. Find seep (mat, hydrate, carbonate)
2. Take a set of 8 push cores if you can and a rock if you see one
3. Transit to WP1, find a good collection site
4. When you see them, collect a diversity of organisms (SEE TABLE)
5. **Slurp mat** (use same chamber at multiple sites)
6. Take a mussel pot (**Bathymodiolus**)
 - a. Only turn T-handle counter-clockwise when handling

- b. Push into coral, turning counter-clockwise
 - c. When it's in, engage ram on manipulator
 - d. Turn pot clockwise
 - e. Keep turning until you see the black mark on string
 - f. Pick it up and return to holster
7. Head towards WPT 2
 - a. Collect animals, 2nd mussel pot, 8 push cores, rocks
 8. Head towards WPT 3
 - a. Collect animals, 3rd mussel pot, 8 push cores, rocks
 9. Head towards WPT 4
 - a. Collect animals, 8 push cores, rocks
 10. Head towards WPT 5
 - a. Collect animals, more push cores, rocks
 11. trip 3 Niskins **CLOSE TO THE END OF THE DIVE** (near mussels, mats, bubbles, something seepy) then continue until all the basket is loaded
 12. If you reach the top of the feature, just run across the platform until the end of dive

Mussel Collections:

3 different patch sizes (small, medium, large, 3-5 each patch)

Target different mussel sizes – no need to actually measure them on the seafloor
dead shells

Push core plan:

8 by mussels

8 by clams

2 sets of 8 in mats

Niskin plan:

1 niskin (#1 or 2) in bubbles

3 Niskins in seepy habitat

Rock plan:

variety of sites (Nancy/Jason to guide), 2-3

RB-1903 – DEEP SEARCH

Dive: J2-1138

Launch: 1200 on 04/29/19

Site: Richardson West

31.8884N, -77.6964W

31 53.311N, -77 41.792W

Depth: 723 m

Corals	Ideal collection needs	location
Lophelia	1 big collection, 10 small	biobox, 3 mussel pots
Enallopsammia	>10	quivers
Desmophyllum	>10	quivers or biobox
Madrepora	?	quivers or biobox
Plumarella	10	quivers
white plexaurid	10	quivers
other octocorals	opportunistic	quivers
other cup corals	opportunistic	quivers

Other critter needs	Ideal collection needs	location
Eumunida	opportunistic	slurp
Other squat		
lobsters	opportunistic	slurp
Asteroschema	opportunistic	biobox/quivers/slurp
Echinus	opportunistic	biobox
Sponges	opportunistic	

Basket: 11 push cores on port swing arm, 8 sample quivers on stbd swing arm, 2 sample quivers on the sled, 4 niskins, 5-chamber slurp, 2 large bioboxes (6 inserts), 3 markers, 3 coral pots, milk crate for ROCKS

All quivers ON STARBOARD SWINGARM except #7 are set up for microbial samples – only 1 species in each (3 minimum, 5 ideal Enallopsammia or Lophelia)

Imagery:

Make sure lasers are on for all transits, off for glamor shots

White balance (one push) when sitting down or starting transiting

Set up shot, then hands off controller for 10-20 secs

Notes: Watch leads should take copious notes in notebook, **if you see trash, pick it up if it doesn't impact science or is dangerous.**

1. Take a set of push cores if you can and a rock if you see one
2. Transit to WP1, find a good coral collection site

3. When you see them, collect a diversity of corals (**SEE TABLE**)
 - a. Octocorals, antipatharians, Enallopsammia into quivers
 - b. Scleractinians into biobox (Lophelia, Desmophyllum, Madrepora)
4. Take a coral pot
 - a. Only turn T-handle counter-clockwise when handling
 - b. Push into coral, turning counter-clockwise
 - c. When it's in, engage ram on manipulator
 - d. Turn pot clockwise
 - e. Keep turning until you see the black mark on string
 - f. Pick it up and return to holster
5. Head towards WPT 2
 - a. Collect corals, 2nd coral pot, more push cores, rocks
6. Head towards WPT 3
 - a. Collect corals, last coral pot, more push cores, rocks
7. trip 3 Niskins **CLOSE TO THE END OF THE DIVE** (near lots of corals)
8. Come home

Appendix D - Jason Dive Summaries

ROV Jason Daily Report

Cruise Number: RB 19-03

Dive number: J2-1128

Chief Scientist: Erik Cordes

Report Date: 4/11/2019

Expedition Leader: Alberto Collasius Jr.

Prepared By: Expedition Leader

Vessel Location: Atlantic 32N 78W

Weather: Good for launch / At limit for recovery

Dive Times: GMT

Dive Activities / Future Activities:

Coral pots, Push cores, Coral samples to quivers, Samples to Bio Box's, Reson and slurp mounted but not utilized

Reason for Dive Termination: Objectives completed

Dive No.	Dates	Max Depth	Hours Descending	Hours Ascending	Hours on Bottom	Hours in water	Time On Deck	Time on Deck not available to science
J2-1128	4/10-4/11	792	:50	2:45	9:30	13:05		0

Completed Dive Summaries:

Vehicle Status: No problems with vehicle.

Weather Forecast:

Weather models have showers in your vicinity right thru Sat morning. Not much on satellite and radar right now. I think the best chance of a few showers will be tonight. I also think the windiest/roughest conditions will be late today thru tomorrow morning. Keep in mind, 1 heavy shower will be followed by a 30-60 minute wind speed lull, but on the leading edge of a heavy shower, winds could gust to 30-34 kts. Quietest conditions of the next 5 days will be Sat afternoon and evening. S winds will be increasing Sun and Sun night will feature strong, gusty winds and thunderstorms. Clearing skies Mon morning. Windy and rough, but it will start to improve Mon afternoon.

Expedition Leader Comments:

Great dive. Landed right on target. Typical first dive with a few teething pains. Wrap counter and dp to Control vans not functioning yet but should be soon. Bridge driving went very well. Sampling went well. As we started ascent the engineer had to go do wakeups and a bad wrap occurred that was noticed as soon as they got back. Had a little trouble adjusting levelwind but 1 call to Fred and we were getting things in order.

Chief Scientist Comments:

This was a very successful dive. The primary goal was to ground-truth our multibeam and test our conceptual models of coral distribution. We spent a good deal of time in the beginning of the dive going through the camera controls with our cinematographer, and he had some helpful pointers, primarily the utilization of the auto white balance button any time that the distance of the subject changes significantly (i.e. sitting down vs. transiting). We are also getting some of the kinks out in our use of the event logger and the video system, but this is to be expected for the first dive.

There were abundant live corals and mounds of coral rubble throughout. It was truly a target-rich environment, and we utilized most of the different types of sampling gear including the bioboxes, coral quivers, and coral (mussel) pots. All of the pilots did an excellent job with the various collections. We did not use the push cores because of the sediment type (there was no sediment), or the slurp sampler due to a lack of suitable targets. Some of the coral quivers were hard to reach, so we are going to adjust the placement of the cores and quivers on the swing arms. One of the bioboxes (our own, not Jason group's) came up a bit warm, so we worked on the seal during the surface interval. The science party commented that the niskins were in an excellent position and they worked well and the Jason group is thanked for their efforts in rigging these bottles.

Contact Numbers:

WHOI / NDSF

Vessel Other

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ROV Jason Daily Report

Cruise Number: RB 19-03

Dive number: J2-1129

Chief Scientist: Erik Cordes

Report Date: 4/14/2019

Expedition Leader: Alberto Collasius Jr.

Prepared By: Expedition Leader

Vessel Location: Atlantic 32N 78W

Weather: Had to delay launch for weather. It layed down enough for launch but was coming back up late am so recovered 8am

Dive Times: GMT

Dive Activities/Future Activities:

Coral pots, Coral samples to quivers, Samples to Bio Box's, Reson and McLane pump deploy and recover

Reason for Dive Termination: Weather

Dive No.	Dates	Max Depth	Hours Descending	Hours Ascending	Hours on Bottom	Hours in water	Time On Deck	Time on Deck not available to science
J2-1128	4/10-4/11	792	:50	2:45	9:30	13:05		0
J2-1129	4/13-4/14	746	1:07	1:20	11:15	13:42	56:53	32:53

Completed Dive Summaries:

Vehicle Status: No problems with vehicle. Need to dial in a few of the views to Both upper and lower Niskins

Weather Forecast: Forecast to deteriorate significantly today

Large low pressure system moving NE across the midwest this morning, and is trailing a strong cold front through the south. Strong squall line of thunderstorms (with severe weather) is moving E and will pass across FL Panhandle this afternoon, shifting off the South Carolina coast by close to midnight tonight. Winds will increase from the S this evening up to 30-40kt and gusts to 50+kt possible. I can't rule out the chance for an isolated waterspouts and some thunder/lightning within this squall line, which should pass near you between 2am and 8am tomorrow. S winds shift into the W behind the front, and wind speeds a little lower. Skies should clear within a few hours after the squall line passes, with winds then diminishing and veering through late Mon into Tues. Fair weather and lighter winds/seas expected for most of Tues and Wed. Thurs we could have another cold front moving across the South, poised to shift offshore before the end of the week.

Expedition Leader Comments:

Good dive. 1.6 knots of surface current. Had to dial in the levelwind a few times and not sure we have it spot on. Had tested at transition during descent but still had troubles with cable laying in nicely during ascent. Launch and recovery went very well except for Level wind issues. Akel got the ship dialed in spot on. Sampling went well except lower Niskins did not trip. Due to weather call not all objectives were completed.

Chief Scientist Comments:

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ROV Jason Daily Report

Cruise Number: RB 19-03

Dive number: J2-1130

Chief Scientist: Amanda Demopoulos

Report Date: 4/17/2019

Expedition Leader: Alberto Collasius Jr.

Prepared By: Expedition Leader

Vessel Location: Atlantic 32N 78W

Weather: Very nice for both LAR

Dive Times: GMT

Dive Activities/Future Activities:

Coral pots, Coral samples to quivers, Samples to Bio Box's, Slurp and push cores

Reason for Dive Termination: Objectives completed

Dive No.	Dates	Max Depth	Hours Descending	Hours Ascending	Hours on Bottom	Hours in water	Time On Deck	Time on Deck not available to science
J2-1128	4/10-4/11	792	:50	2:45	9:30	13:05		0
J2-1129	4/13-4/14	746	1:07	1:20	11:15	13:42	56:53	32:53

Completed Dive Summaries:

Vehicle Status: We have an AC ground fault that appears after submersion but disappears during descent. No other problems.

Weather Forecast: Short term looks good. Expected to deteriorate significantly Thursday PM.

Expedition Leader Comments:

Good dive. 2.2 knots of surface current. Sampling went well. Adjusted level wind during descent and had to do no other adjustments. One of the large Niskins spit a hose clamp and slid down enough to not fully close when tripped. I was advised this had small impact on Science.

Chief Scientist Comments:

The goal of this dive was to traverse a mound feature located at Savannah Banks, from the base to the top of the mound, imaging benthic organisms and their associated habitats and collecting specimens and environmental samples. We planned to collect multiple coral species, several sediment push cores, coral pots, rocks, water samples, and slurp mobile taxa, opportunistically. While we were unsuccessful at finding any rocks to sample as a consequence of the environment, we achieved all of the major dive objectives.

The current on bottom was challenging, but the pilots were able to efficiently maneuver and work with the currents. Despite these conditions, the pilots were able to make excellent collections. One of the niskins didn't close completely, but the issue was resolved prior to the next dive. Because the three other niskins fired, we had sufficient water for our sampling needs for the dive. Overall, this was a highly successful dive and the scientists are still working on the samples collected while we prepare for the next one.

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ROV Jason Daily Report

Cruise Number: RB 19-03

Dive number: J2-1131

Chief Scientist: Amanda Demopoulos

Report Date: 4/18/2019

Expedition Leader: Alberto Collasius Jr.

Prepared By: Expedition Leader

Vessel Location: Atlantic 32N 78W

Weather: Very nice for launch. Deteriorating for recovery

Dive Times: GMT

Dive Activities/Future Activities:

Coral pots, Coral samples to quivers, Push cores, rock collection, Samples to Bio Box's, Slurp and push cores

Reason for Dive Termination: Objectives completed

Dive No.	Dates	Max Depth	Hours Descending	Hours Ascending	Hours on Bottom	Hours in water	Time On Deck	Time on Deck not available to science
J2-1128	4/10-4/11	792	:50	2:45	9:30	13:05		0
J2-1129	4/13-4/14	746	1:07	1:20	11:15	13:42	56:53	32:53
J2-1130	4/17	554	1:19	1:06	8:42	11:07	60:47	0
J2-1131	4/17-4/18	1365	1:55	2:10	13:27	17:32	10:27	0

Completed Dive Summaries:

Vehicle Status: We have an AC ground fault that appears after submersion but disappears during descent. No other problems.

Weather Forecast: Looks bad for the next 48 hours.

Expedition Leader Comments:

Good dive. .8 knots of surface current. Sampling went well. Level wind continues to drift. We are planning a test cast with the steel pig before the weather comes up.

Chief Scientist Comments:

The primary objective of the dive was to investigate a steep feature within the Blake Ridge region. Previous Alvin and D2 (ROV, Okeanos) dives to the north and south of the dive target revealed diverse communities of corals and coral communities, so this exploratory dive had the potential for being very exciting, and it did not disappoint. As soon as we reached the seafloor, we encountered diverse coral communities, with several species of octocorals (isidiids, paramuricids, plexaurids, primnoids), black and stony corals represented. Several enormous dead coral skeletons (either black coral or bamboo) were identified and a few of these were collected for microchemical analysis. We observed very few fish species but imaged an interesting cusk eel loaded with parasites.

All of the science objectives were met, and the basket was full. We appreciate the attention the ROV group paid to ensuring that we dived in the correct location, after accounting for current speed and direction. The pilots did an exceptional job collecting a variety of challenging samples that are now keeping the scientists busy for days. They also helped us collect great imagery for the project. We ended up maxing out the cards recording the 4K imagery, but Scotty resolved the problem quickly. Great work!

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ROV Jason Daily Report

Cruise Number: RB 19-03

Dive number: J2-1132

Chief Scientist: Amanda Demopoulos

Report Date: 4/18/2019

Expedition Leader: Alberto Collasius Jr.

Prepared By: Expedition Leader

Vessel Location: Atlantic 35W 75.2W

Weather: Moderate for launch. Had a pretty good blow during ops. Delayed recovery to let it come down. Blew 30 knots for a few hours.

Dive Times: GMT

Dive Activities/Future Activities:

Coral pots, Coral samples to quivers, Push cores, rock collection, Samples to Bio Box's, Slurp and push cores

Reason for Dive Termination: Objectives completed

Dive No.	Dates	Max Depth	Hours Descending	Hours Ascending	Hours on Bottom	Hours in water	Time On Deck	Time on Deck not available to science
J2-1128	4/10-4/11	792	:50	2:45	9:30	13:05		0
J2-1129	4/13-4/14	746	1:07	1:20	11:15	13:42	56:53	32:53

Completed Dive Summaries:

Vehicle Status: Aft P+T had a .9 ground during dive. No impact on science.

Weather Forecast: Looks better for the next few days.

Expedition Leader Comments:

Very productive dive. 2.7 knots of current for launch. 4 knots of current during recovery. As it was a deeper dive wire angle was the best we had all cruise. Ship lost position 2 times because of Current/Wind combination. Very challenging recovery with current so hi. As we went to launch vehicle ship came to the end of a position move. It was noticed while unlatching. Good catch. I have spoken with bridge about not doing short position moves in high current areas

Chief Scientist Comments:

We had a great dive at Pamlico Canyon today. The seafloor at the start of the dive was composed of heavily sedimented, sloped terrain, with moderate marine snow in the water column. Throughout the dive, while heading upslope along the waypoints, we observed a few species of coral (Acanthogorgia, Solenosmilia, Desmophyllum) that occupied the underside of ledges and several brisingid seastars on the sides of steep features. Push cores were collected at the base of the canyon, and along the steps opportunistically. Several coral samples were collected into the quivers, bioboxes, and coral pots, sometimes on the fly with a scoop against steep walls.

The dive was incredibly productive, despite some major sampling challenges due to the steep cliffs and locations of target specimens. The pilots did a great job with the difficult sampling and the scientists met all of their collection objectives. Despite the high current

conditions throughout the dive and weather that came on toward the latter half of the dive, the ROV and ship operators were able to keep the ROV in the water, on the bottom, and sampling. Great work!

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ROV Jason Daily Report

Cruise Number: RB 19-03

Dive number: J2-1133

Chief Scientist: Amanda Demopoulos

Report Date: 4/23/2019

Expedition Leader: Alberto Collasius Jr.

Prepared By: Expedition Leader

Vessel Location: Atlantic 35.7W 74.8W

Weather: Good weather for LAR

Dive Times: GMT

Dive Activities/Future Activities:

Coral pots, Coral samples to quivers, Push cores, rock collection, Samples to Bio Box's, Slurp and push cores

Reason for Dive Termination: Objectives completed

Dive No.	Dates	Max Depth	Hours Descending	Hours Ascending	Hours on Bottom	Hours in water	Time On Deck	Time on Deck not available to science
J2-1128	4/10-4/11	792	:50	2:45	9:30	13:05		0
J2-1129	4/13-4/14	746	1:07	1:20	11:15	13:42	56:53	32:53
J2-1130	4/17	554	1:19	1:06	8:42	11:07	60:47	0
J2-1131	4/17-4/18	1365	1:55	2:10	13:27	17:32	10:27	0

J2-1132	4/21-4/22	1840	2:53	1:15	23:40	27:48	71:37	0
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Completed Dive Summaries:

Vehicle Status: Got a big Tuna stuck in aft bay for a bit. No other issues

Weather Forecast: Moderate blow expected this evening.

Expedition Leader Comments: Another good dive. All went well till the Tuna attacked. Shut off all lights to try and make it go away. When we turned lights back on Tuna was stuck in aft bay. Went away for a bit once it extracted itself but started on the bow of vehicle again. It hit itself multiple time and seemed to knock itself out and eventually fell backwards off the basket. Not sure Tuna survived.

Chief Scientist Comments:

This was an incredible dive in an area that was recently detected through multibeam mapping efforts and previously imaged by Sentry in 2017. We conducted an Alvin dive at a site ~ 1.5 nm to the northwest of today's dive target. The seep dive was incredibly diverse in terms of fishes, including rock fish, snipe eels, long-finned hake, and midwater fishes, plus we saw lots of schooling fish and shoals of squid. Hammerheads, a manta ray, and a tuna also were observed. We collected rocks and many sediment cores within bacterial mats and bubbles, plus water samples. While collecting a rock, we found a tube worm (Vestimentiferan: cf. Lamellibrachia), which to our knowledge has not be collected along the US Atlantic seeps and could represent a discovery. In addition, we found Lophelia growing on carbonate, which was a nice surprise. All of the scientific objectives were met by the dive and the expert collecting capabilities of the pilots and ROV crew.

We were especially grateful for the pre-dive installation of the core umbrella, which helped protect the gassy cores from escaping from the basket during recovery.

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ROV Jason Daily Report

Cruise Number: RB 19-03

Dive number: J2-1134

Chief Scientist: Amanda Demopoulos

Report Date: 4/24/2019

Expedition Leader: Alberto Collasius Jr.

Prepared By: Expedition Leader

Vessel Location: Atlantic 35.9W 74.8W

Weather: Good weather for Launch. Blew pretty good through the night. Just letting go for recovery

Dive Times: GMT

Dive Activities/Future Activities: Coral pots, Coral samples to quivers, Push cores, rock collection, Samples to Bio Box's, Slurp and push cores

Reason for Dive Termination: Objectives completed

Dive No.	Dates	Max Depth	Hours Descending	Hours Ascending	Hours on Bottom	Hours in water	Time On Deck	Time on Deck not available to science
J2-1128	4/10-4/11	792	:50	2:45	9:30	13:05		0
J2-1129	4/13-4/14	746	1:07	1:20	11:15	13:42	56:53	32:53
J2-1130	4/17	554	1:19	1:06	8:42	11:07	60:47	0
J2-1131	4/17-4/18	1365	1:55	2:10	13:27	17:32	10:27	0

J2-1132	4/21-4/22	1840	2:53	1:15	23:40	27:48	71:37	0
J2-1133	4/23	355	1:10	:32	9:28	11:10	9:15	0

Completed Dive Summaries:

Vehicle Status: Slurp damaged during ops. Intake broke free of hose. This impacted science. Had 2 AFX trips during first few hours of dive. Thoughts are it was GF monitor related.

Weather Forecast: Supposed to lay down this afternoon/evening and come back up tomorrow afternoon

Expedition Leader Comments: Another good dive. Aside from AFX trips and Slurp failure it went very well.

Chief Scientist Comments:

This was the first ROV dive at a known seep environment previously imaged by Sentry in 2017 and waypoints were selected based on confirmed rock, mat, and fish locations from that imagery. The ROV lost power twice and the slurp hose disconnected, but despite these issues, the dive was very successful and the scientists were able to accomplish all of their objectives. We observed dense fish communities at several hard bottom, carbonate features throughout the dive, but the dive track was dominated by soft sediments with lots of sea stars. Given the recovery of a tube worm at the Pea Island seep on the previous dive, we were keen to see if more could be found at Kitty Hawk, and we were very successful. At least 4 more tube worms were collected on this dive; these animals are previously undocumented from the US Atlantic seeps, by collecting rocks from the seafloor. Rock and shell samples were collected to characterize their mineral

composition, enable approximation of the ages of the seep features and constrain the environmental conditions. Sediment was collected at three target environments, bubbles, mats, and background habitats, for geochemical and ecological assessments. Several squat lobsters and quill worms were slurped to provide tissue for molecular and food web studies. Lastly, the niskin samples will be processed for eDNA and microbial community analysis to facilitate community comparisons among seep, canyon, and coral environments.

I've been very pleased with the skill and efficiency of the ROV team, and their attention to detail, all of which have enabled very successful dives thus far on this mission.

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ROV Jason Daily Report

Cruise Number: RB 19-03

Dive number: J2-1135

Chief Scientist: Amanda Demopoulos

Report Date: 4/25/2019

Expedition Leader: Alberto Collasius Jr.

Prepared By: Expedition Leader

Vessel Location: Atlantic 33.5W 74.8W

Weather: Forecast says deteriorating weather. Pretty good for launch. Called dive because winds(mid 20s) were coming up.

Dive Times: GMT

Dive Activities/Future Activities: Coral samples to quivers, Push cores, rock collection, Samples to Bio Box's, Slurp and push cores

Reason for Dive Termination: Weather call

Dive No.	Dates	Max Depth	Hours Descending	Hours Ascending	Hours on Bottom	Hours in water	Time On Deck	Time on Deck not available to science
J2-1128	4/10-4/11	792	:50	2:45	9:30	13:05		0
J2-1129	4/13-4/14	746	1:07	1:20	11:15	13:42	56:53	32:53
J2-1130	4/17	554	1:19	1:06	8:42	11:07	60:47	0
J2-1131	4/17-4/18	1365	1:55	2:10	13:27	17:32	10:27	0

J2-1132	4/21-4/22	1840	2:53	1:15	23:40	27:48	71:37	0
J2-1133	4/23	355	1:10	:32	9:28	11:10	9:15	0
J2-1134	4/24	477	:51	:35	14:46	16:12	7:39	0
J2-1135	4/25	1030	2:05	1:02	2:39	5:48	25:54	0

Completed Dive Summaries:

Vehicle Status: Vehicle in good shape. No problems

Weather Forecast: Forecast calls for the weather to deteriorate significantly .

Expedition Leader Comments: Very good but abbreviated dive. Had a short weather window and took advantage of it.

Chief Scientist Comments:

This exploratory dive examined a target identified in a coral suitability model for the region, representing a validation test of the model. The start of the dive at the base of a steep feature was composed of soft sediments, surprisingly interspersed with small bacterial microbial mats. We collected slurp and core samples at the mats before heading to the steep slope. While traversing upslope, we encountered large boulders that were colonized with encrusting sponges of various colors and a few different corals. These boulders were dramatic features on the scanning sonar and possibly represent a previously unknown landslide feature. The rock collection will be characterized to better understand the broader geological

feature. Attached to these rocks, we observed a fairly diverse assemblage of deep-sea corals from at least five different families. Given the short dive duration, we targeted collections of a few of the dominant corals in order to aid in species identification and contribute to food-web studies. Niskins were tripped at the end of the dive by the corals.

We were pleased that all the equipment worked and that we were able to do this short exploratory dive before the weather picked up. The ROV operators did an excellent job, progressing through the collections in an efficient manner. This helped address a number project objectives and will improve the validate the habitat suitability models developed to improve our understanding of the distribution of deep-sea corals.

Contact Numbers:

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ROV Jason Daily Report

Cruise Number: RB 19-03

Dive number: J2-1136

Chief Scientist: Amanda Demopoulos

Report Date: 4/28/2019

Expedition Leader: Alberto Collasius Jr.

Prepared By: Expedition Leader

Vessel Location: Atlantic 32.4W 76.2W

Weather: Fair

Dive Times: GMT

Dive Activities/Future Activities: Coral samples to quivers, Mussel pots, Push cores, rock collection, Samples to Bio Box's, Slurp and push cores

Reason for Dive Termination: Allotted time up

Dive No.	Dates	Max Depth	Hours Descending	Hours Ascending	Hours on Bottom	Hours in water	Time On Deck	Time on Deck not available to science
J2-1128	4/10-4/11	792	:50	2:45	9:30	13:05		0
J2-1129	4/13-4/14	746	1:07	1:20	11:15	13:42	56:53	32:53
J2-1130	4/17	554	1:19	1:06	8:42	11:07	60:47	0
J2-1131	4/17-4/18	1365	1:55	2:10	13:27	17:32	10:27	0

J2-1132	4/21-4/22	1840	2:53	1:15	23:40	27:48	71:37	0
J2-1133	4/23	355	1:10	:32	9:28	11:10	9:15	0
J2-1134	4/24	477	:51	:35	14:46	16:12	7:39	0
J2-1135	4/25	1030	2:05	1:02	2:39	5:48	25:54	0
J2-1136	4/27-4/28	2169	1:33	1:45	8:46	12:04	21:09	0

Completed Dive Summaries:

Vehicle Status: A Ground fault tripped the AFX right after leaving bottom. Had to give it 2 tries before it came back. Vehicle in good shape otherwise

Weather Forecast: Fair seas and Moderate winds

Expedition Leader Comments: Very good dive other than afx trip. 1.8 knots of surface current for launch. .4 Knots for recovery. 2200 meter dive so wire angle stayed nice for dive

Chief Scientist Comments: This was a great dive exploring Blake Ridge seeps. Our primary goal was to target collections at mussel beds, bacterial mats, and carbonate rock environments, while also characterizing the environment via high resolution imagery. The dive was a great success and we were able to accomplish all of our objectives. We set down on bottom and transited toward waypoints selected based on previous Alvin dives in 2003 and found several old bucket lid markers and Robert Carney's colonization experiment. The

experiment was a bucket filled with oyster shells and rabbit food, and after inspecting the lid, we found Bathymodiolus mussels and anemones attached. During the transit around the site between waypoints, we encountered dense mussel beds, dead clam beds, bacterial mats, and an exciting hydrate mound. We collected some amazing imagery at the mound feature that included two Gaidropsarus sp. fish (rocklings) hanging out in the crevice underneath solid methane hydrate. Really incredible. Several of the collections required precise manipulator skills and the pilots accomplished the tasks with ease. The dive went well and the power failure had no impact on the science.

Contact Numbers:

WHOI / NDSF

Vessel Other

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ROV Jason Daily Report

Cruise Number: RB 19-03

Dive number: J2-1137

Chief Scientist: Amanda Demopoulos

Report Date: 4/29/2019

Expedition Leader: Alberto Collasius Jr.

Prepared By: Expedition Leader

Vessel Location: Atlantic 32.4W 76.2W

Weather: Fair for launch, 24 knots of wind for recovery

Dive Times: GMT

Dive Activities/Future Activities: Coral samples to quivers, Mussel pots, Push cores, rock collection, Samples to Bio Box's, Slurp and push cores

Reason for Dive Termination: Allotted time up

Dive No.	Dates	Max Depth	Hours Descending	Hours Ascending	Hours on Bottom	Hours in water	Time On Deck	Time on Deck not available to science
J2-1128	4/10-4/11	792	:50	2:45	9:30	13:05		0
J2-1129	4/13-4/14	746	1:07	1:20	11:15	13:42	56:53	32:53
J2-1130	4/17	554	1:19	1:06	8:42	11:07	60:47	0
J2-1131	4/17-4/18	1365	1:55	2:10	13:27	17:32	10:27	0

J2-1132	4/21-4/22	1840	2:53	1:15	23:40	27:48	71:37	0
J2-1133	4/23	355	1:10	:32	9:28	11:10	9:15	0
J2-1134	4/24	477	:51	:35	14:46	16:12	7:39	0
J2-1135	4/25	1030	2:05	1:02	2:39	5:48	25:54	0
J2-1136	4/27-4/28	2169	1:33	1:45	8:46	12:04	21:09	0

Completed Dive Summaries:

Vehicle Status: Vehicle in very good working order

Weather Forecast: Fair seas and Moderate winds

Expedition Leader Comments: Great dive. No problems at all.

Chief Scientist Comments: This dive at Cape Fear helped us groundtruth some seep targets identified by Sentry in 2012. We found extensive bacterial mats, what appeared to be frenulate tubeworm patches, and carbonate rock. On several rock features we found corals, including *Anthomastus* and *Chrysogorgia*, and large sponges, as well as different fishes. We encountered odd shaped tubular mud rocks that have been previously observed at the northeast US Canyons. All of the collections were challenging due to the extremely swift currents at depth (even at 2600m!), complex bathymetry, and fragile specimens, but the pilots rose to the challenge and accomplished all of our dive objectives. Great job!

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Appendix B - Plans of the Day (PODs)

Appendix C - Dive Plans

Appendix D - Jason Dive Summaries